

**VALIDATION AND STANDARDISATION OF A TOOL
TO ASSESS SATTVABALA**

By

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Dissertation submitted to

**RAJIV GANDHI UNIVERSITY OF HEALTH SCIENCES, KARNATAKA,
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In

MANOVIGYANA AVAM MANASAROGA

Under the guidance of

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

A.H	Ashtanga Hridaya
A.S	Ashtanga Sangraha
B.P	Bhavaprakasha
B.S	Bhela Samhita
B.T.T	Bhattacharya T.T
B.P.N	Bhavaprakasha Nighantu
B.R	Bhaisajya Ratnavali
C.S	Charaka Samhita
Chha. Up	Chhandogya Upanishad
D.N	Dhanwantari Nighandu
H.S	Haritha Samhita
K.S	Kashyapa Samhita
M.N	Madhava Nidana
M.M.W	Monier M. William
R.N	Raja Nighantu
Sa	Sharangadhara Samhita
S.K	Sabda Kalpadruma
S.S	Sushruta Samhita
Y.R	Yogaratnakara

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AH.Ni	Ashtanga Hridaya Nidanastana
AH.Sa	Ashtanga Hridaya Sareerastana
AH.Soo	Ashtanga Hridaya Sootrastana
AS.Ni	Ashtanga Sangraha Nidanastana
CH.Chi	Charaka Samhita Chikitsastana
CH.Soo	Charaka Samhita Sootrastana
SU.Chi	Susrutha samhitha Chikitsastana
SU.Soo	Susrutha samhitha Sootrastana
SU.U	Susrutha samhitha Uttarastana
SU.Sa	Susrutha samhitha Sareerastana
SU. Ni.	Susrutha samhitha Nidanastana
PCA	Principle component analysis

Symbols

=	Equal to
%	Percentage
>	Greater than
<	Lesser than

LIST OF TABLES

Sl. No	Tables	Page No.
1	Table 1- Derivatives of sattva as per different authors	5
2	Table 2- Laxana of Sattvasara Purusha	10-11
3	Table 3 – No of Domains and No of Items each domain	27
4	Table no.4 &5 – Expert evaluation form	28
5	Table no.6: KMO measure and interpretation	33
6	Table no.7: Draft 1 and 2 of Assessment tool	36
7	Table no 8-61: Pilot Test Results	44-63
8	Table No 62-115 : Results on 300 participants	64-91
9	Domainwise internal reliability and suitability of data for factor analysis – Table No 116-126	92- 95
10	Cronbach’s Alpha of 45 items -Table No 127	96
11	KMO And Bartlett Test for 300 participants- Table No 128	96
12	Communalities (EFA)Table No 129	97-103
13	Table no.130: Rotated Component Matrix (EFA)	105-126
15	External – by Test -Retest Reliability Table #132	127
16	Table #133 - Item Analysis	127-131
17	Table 134- Descriptive Statistics	132-34
18	Table 135 – Communalities(CFA)	136-37
19	Table 136 -Total Variance Explained	138-9
20	Table #137 -Rotated Component Matrix	141-44

LIST OF FIGURES

Sl. No	Figures	Page No.
1.	Steps in tool development	17
2.	Scree plot	140
3.	Component plot in rotated space	145

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Section No.	Topics	Page No.
1	Introduction	1-3
2	Objectives	1-3
3	Review of literature	4-24
4	Methodology	25-40
5	Sample Size Estimation	41-43
6	Observation and Results	44-282
7	Discussion	283-302
8	Conclusion	303- 305
9	Summary	306-308
10	Bibliographic References	309-315
12	Annexures	316-545

ABSTRACT

Title: Validation and Standardisation of a tool to assess Sattvabala

Background: The concept of *Sattvabala*, rooted in Ayurveda, encompasses mental clarity, emotional stability, and overall psychological resilience to combat adversities. This study aimed to validate and standardize a tool designed to assess *Sattvabala*, thus providing a reliable measure for both clinical and research purposes. The development process included a comprehensive literature review, expert consultations, and iterative feedback to ensure the tool's relevance and comprehensiveness. A cross-sectional study was conducted involving a diverse sample of participants, including practitioners of Ayurveda and individuals seeking holistic health assessments. Factor analysis was employed to ascertain the underlying structure of the assessment tool, while reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha and test-retest methods. The results demonstrated strong psychometric properties, with the final version of the tool comprising multiple dimensions that accurately reflect the constructs of *Sattvabala*. This standardized tool not only enhances the assessment of sattva in clinical practice but also provides a foundational framework for future research exploring the interplay between psychological states and physical health. The findings underscore the importance of incorporating traditional concepts into contemporary health assessments, promoting a more holistic understanding of well-being.

Keywords: Sattvabala, validation, standardization, psychometric properties, Ayurveda, mental health assessment.

Objectives: To validate and standardize an Ayurveda assessment tool for Sattvabala.

Methods:

This study outlines the methodology applied to validate and standardize a newly developed tool for assessing *Sattvabala*, a core concept in Ayurveda representing mental and emotional resilience. The research was conducted in several phases:

1. **Tool Development:** Initially, an extensive literature review was performed to define *Sattvabala* and identify relevant indicators. Expert consultations with Manasaroga practitioners, language experts and psychologists were conducted to generate a comprehensive item pool, capturing different dimensions of *Sattvabala*.
2. **Pilot Testing:** A preliminary version of the assessment tool was administered to a small group of participants (n=18) to evaluate clarity and relevance of the items. Feedback was collected to refine the tool.
3. **Main Study Design:** A cross-sectional study was conducted with a diverse sample of 300 healthy participants ranging in age, gender, and cultural background. Participants were sent across google forms.
4. **Data Collection:** The refined *Sattvabala* tool, consisting of 45 items on a 3-point Likert scale, was distributed alongside established measures of psychological resilience and well-being for comparative analysis. Demographic data were also collected.
5. **Statistical Analysis:** Factor analysis (Principal Component Analysis) was performed to determine the dimensional structure of the tool, while reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha to evaluate internal consistency. Test-retest reliability was examined with a subset of participants (n=300) within the next few weeks.
6. **Validity Assessment:** Construct validity was assessed by correlating scores from the *Sattvabala* tool with external measures of mental health and emotional well-being. Content validity was established through expert reviews and qualitative feedback.

ABSTRACT

7. **Standardisation Phase:** 28 items were retained from the 45 items scale post CFA and a 28 item questionnaire was sent across 500 participants (250 healthy and 250 patients of Common Mental Disorders) and cut off scores were finalised based on Normality tests and Z score calculation
8. **Finalization of Tool:** Findings from the analysis led to the finalization of a 28-item assessment tool, showcasing robust psychometric properties indicating high reliability and validity.

RESULTS: The observations are presented in the form of tables and graphs. The developed assessment tool displays Cronbach's alpha and KMO values that are statistically significant. As a result, the tool has been appropriately validated. Further norm development results and cut off scores are compiled in tables and the final scale is framed.

Conclusion: The study provides an assessment tool which is validated and standardized on Sattvabala. After the thorough research through Samhitas and other related texts, a total of 28 items were standardized post validation following the steps in tool development.

Keywords: Sattvabala, validation, standardization, psychometric properties, Ayurveda, mental health assessment.

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION**VALIDATION AND STANDARDIZATION OF A TOOL TO ASSESS SATTVA BALA**

Sattvabala is an ayurveda parameter described to assess the distress tolerance of an individual in daily living. It is the strength of an individual to remain calm in experiences of excitement or lassitude that helps in maintaining the wellbeing. Charaka and Sushruta explain the concept, identifying and highlighting its role in sound functioning of an individual in the personal and social grounds. A physical and psychological assessment stands incomplete without the assessment of sattvabala as Charaka places this variable in the Dashavidha pareeksha (10-fold examination). (1) Graded as *Avara*, *Madhyama* and *Pravara* types of *sattva* based on ascending strength, it holds prognostic and therapeutic value at assessing treatment outcomes in patients and evaluating an early risk factor for a future disease in healthy population. Planning a therapy also relies upon the receptivity of the person which again relies upon the sattvabala. Despite being documented as early as 2nd Century BC in Ayurveda texts; this variable is yet to be completely understood, studied at the individual and community for its clinical and epidemiological value shows the dearth in research on *Sattvabala*. Hence the current work is taken upon to develop, validate and standardize a tool to assess the sattvabala.

Tool development and validation has 3 steps. Such as item generation, tool development and tool evaluation: (2) An extensive literature search (charaka samhita, sushruta samhita, ashtanga hrdaya, ashtanga sangraha, sabdakalpadruma, vachaspatya, moneir williams and amarakosha) revealed the relevant meanings and definitions of

INTRODUCTION

each term, and domains were constructed based on this. Further, items were generated for each domain and the construct was undergone for content validity and face validity assessments.

Then the assessment tool was administered to a larger population and evaluated by the application of various reliability and validity assessments like cronbach's alpha.

Factor analysis was conducted and finally an assessment tool was generated with 10 domains and 28 items and standardised.

OBJECTIVES

Objectives

To validate and standardize an Ayurveda assessment tool for Sattvabala.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Sattva nomenclature

Human life is a manifestation of synergism of Atma and Shareera along Sattva. Sabdakalpadruma defines sattva as, 'Sato bhaavasattva' (sat + tva = sattvam). where the root 'sat' means- 'reality', 'truth', 'excellent', 'being present', 'exist' etc.(3) Similarly 'tva' denotes essence. Presently, it can be understood as the human composite to execute mental restraint, to stay real. According to Sir Monier William's Dictionary, the meaning of sattva is many folds; being existing, true essence, disposition of mind, spiritual essence, vital breath, life, consciousness, strength, firmness, energy, wisdom. Acharyas (pioneers in the field of Ayurveda) have used the term sattva as a synonym of 'manas' or the mental faculty. Manas is treated as internal organ of perception. The term 'manas' is defined as 'manyatejnyatemananatmanah' (through which something is known). The root 'man' denotes knowledge. Though sattva is considered as the synonym of mana, it has been used in various contexts by Acharyas (pioneers in the field of ayurveda) denoting personality type, mental strength, and psycho somatic constitution. The word *Sattva* comes from the aphoristic rule *Tasyabhavah tvatalau*, which is formed by adding the suffix 'tva' to the noun 'sat'. Sat is a *Sanskrit* word that means "presence," "being," "reality," "truth," "virtuous," and "wonderful. The numerous synonyms, in fact, represent multiple aspects of *Sattva's* shades/functions. The *sattva* is a sensory organ inside the body. It investigates, reasons, judges, and evaluates the objects

as it perceives them, distinguishes between several aspects of the items It then mulls on the situation. Over to focus and emerges with the truth, which it passes, upon the psyche It also remembers what has been learned and recalls information as needed.

Synonyms of *Sattva*

- *Manas, Sattva and Chitta*
- *Chitta, Hrnmmasam and Hridya (Amarkosha)*

Table 1- Derivatives of sattva as per different authors(4–7)

Sl.no	Textbook	Reference
1	Monier Williams dictionary	true essence, nature, disposition of mind, character vital breath, life, consciousness, strength of character, strength, firmness, energy, resolution, courage, self-command, good sense, wisdom, magnanimity,
2	Charakaa Samhitha	सत्त्वं मनः, मनसो बलं वा यत् ‘उत्साह
3	Sushruta Samhitha	सत्त्वं [१] तु व्यसनाभ्युदयक्रियादिस्थानेष्वक्लवकरम् सत्त्ववान् सहते सर्वं संस्तभ्यात्मानमात्मना
4	Ashtanga Hrudaya	धैर्ययुतो मोहवर्जितः धैर्यम्, तस्मात्सत्त्वदेहबलाबलाद्धेतोर्गुर्वल्पव्याधिसंस्थानेऽवहितो भवेत्
5.	Ashtanga Sangraha	सत्त्वं मनः विधेयमपरवशम्
6	Laxana Kosha	Sahatwam na kaalata naiva sarvasya
7	Shabdakalpadruma	sattvam prakashaka jnanam sukhahetu

Nature of *sattva*

According to *Ayurveda*, the *sattva* is one of the four main components of life, and it is regarded the tripod on which the individual is raised and works, along with the *atma* and the *shareera*. The body is inert and incapable of providing its own motivation; the soul, on the other hand, is beyond the realm of action but offers inclination just by being present. The soul can only achieve this if the *sattva* with which it is linked also suggests sensory perception and controls the sensory process. It is also known as transcending senses because it is thought to experience feelings like as pleasure and pain regardless of sensory apparatus.

It is part of the triangle of internal perception, together with Ego and intellect. Understanding the object is the only and most significant proof of the *sattva's* existence; otherwise, unlike the soul, which is omnipresent and pervasive, the *sattva* is atomic and unitary. The *sattva* is inextricably linked to the *trigunas*, and their relative dominance is accountable for the tripartite character of the *sattva*. The *sattva* is recognized as a matter and is one of the nine basic substances. The *sattva's* principal role is to activate and regulate the sense organ's function as well as to manage its own actions.

Sattava bala (1)

We can find a detailed description of the 10 most important factors for clinical examination in *Vimana Sthana*. When describing the *Desha* examination, *acharya*

Charakaa emphasized that the *desha* encompasses both the *bhoomi* and the *atura*. To determine the patient's complete knowledge and medications, a land examination is required. The examination of a patient is necessary to obtain complete knowledge about a patient, such as his place of birth, his place of growth and development, where he was afflicted by the disease, the circumstances and peculiar features of the people in the area where he was afflicted by the disease, food, exercise, and the homologation of the people in that area, and so on. The knowledge of the patient and the medicines can be determined by examining the land. According to this the physician should investigate the patient's Ten major factors viz.

1. *Prakrti* -Somatic constitution
2. *Vikrti* –Morbidity
3. *Sara* -Strength of bodily system
4. *Samhanana* -Compactness of the body
5. *Pramana*-Measurements of the different bodily organs
6. *Satmya* –Homologation
7. *Sattva* -'Mental state/psychiatric assessment
8. *Aharasakti*-Food intake and digestive capacity
9. *Vyayama sakti* -Exercise Performance Capacity
10. *Vayastah* -Age, to determine the strength of the patient and intensity of the disease.

Out of these Ten factors, the seventh one is the *Sattva*, considered as *Mano Bala* and is an outstanding diagnostic measure. Basing upon the *Bala* (Strength) the *Sattva* (Manas) is of three types. Viz. *Pravara*(superior), *Madhyama* (Mediocre) and *Avara* (inferior). The human beings are classified into three groups based on their *Manobala* viz.

a) *Pravara Sattva*

b) *Madhyama Sattva*

c) *Avara sattva*

a) *Pravara Sattva* (1)

The people who possess the qualities of *Sattva Sara* are considered to be *Pravara sattva/Uttama Sattva*. The *Pravara Sattva* individuals have good tolerance to diseases caused by *Nija* (Endogenous) and *Agantuja* (Exogenous) factors, in spite of having weak physique (*Swalpa Sarira*). A man of *Sattvika* temperament (having a good quantum of *Sattva*) is capable of bearing anything or any amount of agony by portraying his *Manas* with the help of *Atma*. Individuals having an increased (amount) of *Sattva Guna* are thought to be of

Uttama Manobala, and as a result, they are capable of enduring painful activities.

b) *Madhyama Sattva* (1)

Individuals who possess *Madhyama Sattva* have the ability to withstand sickness and other ailments, and when they realise that others can tolerate the same, they take strength from others. By using persuasive advice and the logic of the inevitable, a man with *Rajasa guna* of can be persuaded to calmly submit to a course of event. Individuals with a high level of *Rajo Guna* are *Madhyama Manobala*, and as a result, they can tolerate painful acts if they are given a clear and rational explanation of the disease's significance and the importance of care.

c) *Avara sattva* (1)

Even if the *Avara Sattva* persons have a good physique (Plump), they have little tolerance/patience capacity for even a minor illness. The *Avara Sattva* folks cannot bear *Manobala* to resist sickness or misery by witnessing others or by themselves. Dread, grief, greed, delusion, and egoism are all too strong for these people. *Avara Sattva* persons are afflicted by despair, pallor, fainting, madness, dizziness, or they may faint and fall on the ground after listening to stories containing wrath, fear, hate, terror, and deformed/disfigured scenes, or by viewing the blood or flesh of an animal or human being. The possibility of bodily discomfort just overwhelms a man of *Tāmasa guna*. Individuals with a high level of *tamo guna* are said to be in *Manodaurbalya* (weak mind), and they are unable tolerate distress either by themselves, by seeing others, or by explaining the actions of others.

Keeping in view of the above references one can correlate the opinions of

Charaka and *Susruta* as follows:

1. *Pravara Sattva = Sattva Pradhana Uttama Manobala*

2. *Madhyama Sattva = Rajah Pradhana Madhyama Manobala*

3. *Avara Sattva= Tamah Pradhina Mano daurbalya*

Sattva sara (1)

In addition to the notion of trividha sattva, the Ayurvedic Classics also introduced the concept of Sattva Sara in the context of *Sara Pariksha*. In the *Charaka Samhita*, it is said that *pravara satva* and *sattvasara* are synonymous. following traits are mentioned by Acharya *Charakaa* under *sattvasara* . Sattvasarata contributes to sattvabala as Charaka says *sattvasara purusha* as *uttama sattva purusha*. Hence diminishing sara also diminishes the *sattvabala*.

Table 2- Laxana of Sattvasara Purusha(1)

Sr.No	Ayurveda Traits	Modern Traits
1	<i>Smritimanto</i>	Good Memory
2	<i>Bhaktimantah</i>	Devotion
3	<i>Kritajna</i>	Gratefulness
4	<i>Prajna</i>	Wisdom
5	<i>Shuchi</i>	Purity
6	<i>Mahotsaha</i>	Excessive enthusiasm
7	<i>Daksha</i>	Skill
8	<i>Dheera</i>	Courage
9	<i>Smara vikarantah yodhi</i>	Valour in fighting
10	<i>Tyaktavishada</i>	Absence of sorrow
11	<i>Suvyavasthitagatti</i>	Proper gait
12	<i>Gambhirdudhhi</i>	Depth of wisdom
13	<i>Chesta</i>	Sincerity of action
14	<i>Kalayanaabhinivesha</i>	Virtuous acts

1. Smritimanta = स्मृतिः अतीतार्थविषयज्ञानं

Endowed with superior memory, these individuals can manage their activities without distress as they are well prepared due to their past experiences. They learn from their past mistakes; they recollect from the past and reform their actions.

2. Bhaktimanta = भक्तिः इच्छेत्यर्थः; रुचिः-भक्तिः

Bhakti means ruchi /iccha. It is understood as interests/desire of the individual to engage in activities beyond their boundaries. These individuals dedicate themselves, unwavering as they are inclined to completion of the work owing to their desire/interest. They look beyond the distress coming their way as they seek their interests looking past the hurdles.

3. Krutjna = Krutam upakrutam jaanati sweekaroti va

Someone who acknowledges, respects the favours received and remains grateful to them are termed to be krutajna. These individuals are humble, respectful and responsible in their actions as they are aware of their existence being dependent on the people around them. When encountering with distress their humble approach towards distress lets them face distress with ease.

4. Prajna = प्रज्ञा कालत्रयात्मिका बुद्धिः

These individuals are mindful about the past, present and future and hence plan ahead in their endeavors. Their strategies minimize the stressors due to ‘prajanaparadha’ and they are equipped with experiences of the past to face the distress in the present with minimum compulsions. The appropriate interaction of dhee, dhriti and smriti of theirs helps them to restraint their ‘indriyas – indriyarthas’ sannikarsha, thus promoting sattva guna and hence the sattvabala.

5. Shuchi = शुचिर्मनोवाक्कायैः शुद्धः।

Cleanliness and purity in terms of physical, psychological and verbal conduct. A clean body, mind and behaviour enhances the sattva by perceiving arthas that are only beneficial to the indriyas, ignoring the others. This is attained only by practice, as it gradually enhances the dhee and dhriti component, thereby increasing the buddhi and strengthening the sattva. References of sattva guna also stresses on the word ‘shuchi’ as a primary quality, highlighting the relation of sattva with shuchitva.

6. Mahotsaha = ऊर्जा- उत्साहः,

It is the energy/enthusiasm shown by the individual in a task/event. It reflects the strength, tolerance to lead the way towards its completion. ‘Urja/ Utsaha’ are synonymous to sattva. Brighter the energy, stronger the sattva of the individual. In the context, books of Ashtanga and

Sushruta highlight 'alasya' as antagonizing action to utsaha, indication of a poor sattvabala.

7. Daksha = कर्मणि चतुरः

Cleverness/smartness of the individual is an indicative of superior sattva as they accomplish tasks with minimum errors and maximum efficiency. These traits make them favourable in the crowd of less efficient individuals.

8. Dheera & Samaravikrantayodhi = धैर्यं धीरत्वं - समरे विक्रम्य युध्यन्तीति समरविक्रान्तयोधिनः

The courage to carry out the task at hand, measures the 'dheerata' (determination) of the individual. Psychological stability irrespective of the physical stature is responsible for courage in an individual. Dheerata in the form of reassuring about the unknown feeling of the mind is indicative of patience and a non-vulnerable quality of sattvabala. Hence the individual is valiant in the task given until its completion

9. Tyaktavishada = devoid of despair

The definition of uttamasattva emphasis on the calm and composed nature of the individual devoid of any excitement or lassitude in moments of such nature. Charaka again clarifies the same under the context of sattvasara purusha, thus sealing the relation between uttama/pravara sattva with sattvasara purusha.

10. Suvyavasthithagati & gambheerabuddhi-cheshta = Eventful planning and organized activities.

Charaka explaining the behaviour of sattvasara purusha says, the

activities are meaningful, planned and organized and hence productive.

These actions minimize the errors that can cause distress. This kind of behaviour is due to qualities like smriti, prajna, shuchi, krutajna etc mentioned in the same context. Collectively it shows the character and actions of an uttama sattva purusha.

**11. Kalyanabhinivesha = कल्याणाभिनिवेशेनेति श्रेयस्करमार्गानुष्ठानेन;
एतद्धि अचिरभाविश्रेयसामेव भवति**

Sattvaguna comes with kalyanamsha (virtuousness), whereas rajas and tamas guna are associated with rosha (passion/rage) and moha (confusions) respectively as per Ayurveda. Individuals belonging to uttama/pravara sattva are seen to be involved in virtuous deeds for people around them managing their own deeds.

STEPS IN TOOL DEVELOPMENT(2,8)

The tool development is done in 3 steps:

- Item generation and development
- Scale Development
- Scale Evaluation

Figure 1 – Steps of Tool Development

1. Item generation and development

The item development has 2 steps:

- a. Identification of the Domain(s) and Item Generation.
- b. Content Validity

Domain Identification: The first step is to define the domain(s) which is to be measured.

A domain or construct is the concept, trait, or unobserved behavior that is the study's objective. As a result, before engaging in any item activity, the domain under consideration should be determined and defined. A well-defined domain will provide an understanding of the phenomenon under study, clarify the domain boundaries, and make item development and content validation easier. If a preexisting structure or theory is driving the inquiry, domains are determined a priori; otherwise, domains are determined a posteriori.

Item Generation: Once the domain has been defined, the item pool can be recognised.

This procedure is also known as "question development" or "item generation." Deductive and inductive approaches are used to identify relevant questions. The deductive method is based on the description of the relevant domain and the identification of items. It is also known as "logical partitioning" or "classification from above." This can be accomplished by conducting literature research and evaluating current scales and indicators in that subject. The inductive approach, often known as "grouping" or "classification from below," involves the creation of items based on individual responses. Qualitative data gathered through direct observations and exploratory research methods such as focus groups and

individual interviews, can be used to inductively identify domain items. It is considered best practice to combine both deductive and inductive methods to both define the domain and identify the questions to assess it. Further, in the development of items, the form of the items, the wording of the items, and the types of responses that the question is designed to induce should be taken into account.

Content Validity: Content validity, refers to the adequacy with which a measure assesses the domain of interest. It is also known as —theoretical analysis. Content validity specifies content relevance and content representations, i.e., that the items capture the relevant experience of the target population being examined. Content validity is mainly assessed through evaluation by expert and target population judges. Expert judges are highly knowledgeable about the domain of interest and/or scale development; target population judges are potential users of the scale.

2. TOOL DEVELOPMENT

The tool development is done in 4 steps:

- a. Pre-testing Questions
- b. Sampling and Survey Administration
- c. Item Reduction
- d. Extraction of Factors

Pre-testing Questions: Pre-testing helps to ensure that items are meaningful to the target population before the survey is actually administered. It eliminates poorly worded items and facilitates revision of phrasing to be maximally understood. Pre-testing is helpful in

the examination of the extent to which the questions reflect the domain being studied. It also facilitates the examination of the extent to which answers to the questions asked produce valid measurements. The prepared questionnaire has to be pretested in a small sample of 10 to 30 of the target population to refine the questions.

Sampling and Survey Administration:

- Establishing the Sample Size- The sample size required for any given study is determined by various factors, including the level of variance between variables and the level of over-determination (i.e., the ratio of variables to the number of factors) of the factors. A graded scale of sample sizes for scale development is: 100 = poor, 200 = fair, 300 = good, 500 = very good, $\geq 1,000$ = excellent. The rule of thumb has been at least 10 participants for each scale item, i.e., an ideal ratio of respondents to items is 10:1 and it can be applied for sample size estimation.
- Survey Administration- It is critical to collect data with minimal measurement errors from a sufficient sample size. The data can be collected using paper and pen/pencil interviewing (PAPI) or Computer Assisted Personal Interviewing (CAPI) on devices like laptops, tablets, or phones. There are several software programmes available for creating forms on devices, through which data can be collected.

Item Reduction Analysis: Item reduction analysis is used in scale development to make sure that only reasonable, functional and internally consistent items are finally included. Classical Test Theory (CTT) and the Item Response Theory (IRT) are the two theories

which give groundwork to scale development. CTT allows the prediction of outcomes of constructs and the difficulty of items. The goal of item response theory is to model how conceptions appear in terms of observable item response. Depending on which test theory is driving the scale, there are several ways to minimize the item pool within the two theories. The five major techniques used are: item difficulty and item discrimination indices, which are primarily for binary responses; inter-item and item-total correlations, which are mostly used for categorical items; and distractor efficiency analysis for items with multiple choice response options.

Extraction of Factors: Factor extraction is the phase in which the optimal number of factors, sometimes called domains that fit a set of items are determined. Factor Analysis is the method used for this. Factor analysis is a statistical technique that reduces a set of variables by extracting all their commonalities into a smaller number of factors. It can also be called data reduction. When a large number of variables are observed, some common patterns emerge, which are known as factors. These serve as an index of all the variables involved and can be utilized for later analysis. In factor analysis Items with factor loadings or slope coefficients less than 0.30 are considered inadequate in factor analysis since they contribute 10% variance of the latent construct assessed. As a result, it is frequently advised to retain items with factor loadings of 0.40 or higher.

3. TOOL EVALUATION(9,10)

3 tests are preferably used for tool evaluation:

- Tests of Dimensionality
- Tests of Reliability
- Tests of Validity

Tests of Dimensionality: Tests of dimensionality determine whether the measurement of items, their factors, and function are the same across two independent samples or within the same sample at different time points. Such tests can be conducted using independent cluster model (ICM)-confirmatory factor analysis, bifactor modeling, or measurement invariance.

Tests of Reliability: Reliability is the degree of consistency exhibited when a measurement is repeated under identical conditions. A number of standard statistics have been developed to assess reliability of a scale, including Cronbach 's alpha, ordinal alpha specific to binary and ordinal scale items, test-retest reliability, split-half estimates etc. Cronbach 's alpha and test-retest reliability are the most commonly used statistics to determine scale reliability. Cronbach's alpha measures the internal consistency of the scale items, indicating the degree to which the set of scale items co-vary in relation to their total score. The test–retest reliability, also known as the coefficient of stability, is used to assess the degree to which the participants 'performance is repeatable, i.e., how consistent their sum scores are across time. Intra class correlation coefficient and Pearson product-moment correlation are the common tests used.

Tests of Validity: Scale validity is the extent to which an instrument indeed measures the latent dimension or construct it was developed to evaluate. The most common tests of validity are content validity (described in Step 2), which can be done prior to the instrument being administered to the target population, and criterion (predictive and concurrent) and construct validity (convergent, discriminant, differentiation by known groups, correlations), which occurs after survey administration. Validation is an ongoing process that starts with the identification and definition of the domain of study and continues to its generalizability with other constructs.

QUALITIES OF A GOOD TOOL (11)

- Adequate for the problem intended to be measured (content validity)
- Reflect underlying theory or concept to be measured (construct validity)
- Reliability and precision, so that the measurements are consistent
- Feasibility - simple and acceptable to patients and physicians
- Sensitivity to change - capable of measuring change through time.

SCALE STANDARDIZATION(12)

Scale standardization is the process of establishing a norm for a measurement tool (such as a questionnaire or survey) to ensure that it can be accurately and consistently interpreted across different populations or contexts. This is especially crucial when dealing with psychological constructs, such as Sattvabala, to make the scores meaningful and applicable in various settings. Here's a structured approach for standardizing a scale: The method is used for enhancing the assessment and makes a

stable presence. Standardized tests provide a set of normative data (i.e., norms), or scores derived from groups of people for whom the measure is designed (i.e., the designated population) to which an individual's performance can be compared. Norms consist of transformed scores such as percentiles, measures of central tendency, and standard scores (e.g., T-scores, Z-scores, stanines, IQs), allowing for comparison of an individual's test results with the designated population.

METHODOLOGY

METHODOLOGY

METHODOLOGY

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Source of data

1. Literary data:

The data required for the development of an assessment tool was collected from Bruhatrayi, contemporary texts and journals.

2. Survey study:

- In first phase a questionnaire was formed based on the information about Sattva, Sattvabala from various Ayurveda classics.
- In second phase, an assessment tool was constructed and it is further distributed to 10 Ayurveda Academicians and practitioners from Manasa roga, Samhitha siddhanta and Kayachikitsa. Their response has been analyzed and pilot on was conducted.
- In third phase, this formatted assessment tool has been administered to 300 respondents and the data was analyzed for its reliability and validity.

For Validation

Inclusion Criteria:

- Apparently healthy individuals.
- Age group of 18-60 years.
- Subjects willing to sign informed consent and participate.

Exclusion Criteria

- Subjects with any known systemic or mental illnesses.

METHODOLOGY

For Standardisation

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Participants between 18- 60 years of age, irrespective of their health status barring the exclusion criteria.
2. Subjects willing to sign informed consent and participate.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1. Subjects incapable to give valid responses such as acutely ill patients, use of psychoactive substances.

Method of collection of data:

- Method of Data collection: Google Forms
<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfVjb1vvKznQSoNo6I6rge9V-WGcfLLuEGjRIwezJt4T4DEg/viewform>
- Closed ended questionnaire
- Analysis: Suitable statistical tool was used.
- 3 item Likert scale pattern was followed
- Sampling technique: Purposive sampling for questionnaire administration
- Sample size: 800 subjects – 300 for validation and 500 for standardization.

METHODOLOGY

Plan of study

❖ Scale Development

Based on the standard questionnaire validation and standardization criteria the step wise construction of tool was done. This is as follows,

1. ITEM DEVELOPMENT

- a. Identification of domain
- b. Item generation
- c. Content validity

2. SCALE DEVELOPMENT

- a. Pre testing of questionnaire /pilot study
- b. Sampling & survey administration
- c. Internal consistency assessment /Item reduction
- d. Extraction of factors

3. SCALE EVALUATION

- a. Test of reliability
- b. Test of validity

4. SCALE STANDARDISATION

- a. Tests of Normality

ITEM DEVELOPMENT

1. Identification of domain:

- First step in the scale development is identification of domain which refers to specify the boundaries of the domain and facilitate the item generation.

METHODOLOGY

- Based on the available information from Ayurveda texts on Sattva and sattvabala 11 domains were selected from the description of sattvasara purusha laxana of Charaka Samhitha. i.e, Smriti, Bhakti, Krutajna, Prajna, Shuchi, Mahotsaha, Daksha, Dheera, Samaravikrantayodhi, Tyaktavisahda, Suvyavasthithagambeeragatibuddhicheshta, Kalyanabhinivesha.

- The domain Shuchi was subdivided as Kaya shuchi, Vak shuchi and Mano shuchi.
- The information regarding each domain was collected from Ayurveda Texts (Charka Samhita, Susruta Samhita, Ashtanga Hrudaya, Amarakosha, Sabdakalpadruma, Vachaspatya) and contemporary text and journals.
- The data was critically analyzed.
- Based on the available information the workable meanings and their synonyms were considered.
- Certain domains were hence combined for an easier understanding and applicability.

2. Item Generation

- Both Deductive and inductive methods are used for item generation.
- Questions were prepared based on the literature review and assessment of existing scales and indicators of that domain. Focus group discussion and direct observations are also made into account for generating questions.
- Based on the data, Domains, Subdomains and the number of items were decided.(Table no 3)The framed items are allotted with the **3-point Likert scale – indicative of Avara, Madhyama and Pravara sattva respectively.**

METHODOLOGY

Table 3 – No of Domains and No of Items each domain

Domain	Word Meaning		No Of Items
	English	Sanskrit	
1. Smriti	Memory	smarana	4
2. Bhakti	Interest	ruchi	4
3. Krutajna	Gratitude upakaram	janati upakaram, sweekaroti upakaram	3
4. Prajna	Intellectual	Kalatryatmika Buddhi	5
5. Shuchi	K a y a	Cleanliness of body, healthy communication and mind	7(3+2+ 2)
	V a k		
	M a n a		
6. Mahotsaha	Enthusiasm	oorja	4
7. Daksha	Able Samartha		3
8. Dheera and Samaravikrantayodhina	courage/ dheerata		4
9. Tyaktavishada	given up despair		3
10. Suvyavasthithagambhirabuddhi and cheshta	(deerghabuddhi / intelligent reasoning and efforts)		5
11. Kalyanabhinivesha	कल्याणाभिनिवेशं कल्याणविषये यत्नपरम्/ towards common benefit)	efforts are put	2

METHODOLOGY

3. CONTENT VALIDITY

- Questions prepared on each domain was send for expert opinion for 22 members from different fields of Ayurveda like Manasa Roga, Clinical Psychology, English language, and those who have worked upon such studies.
- Briefed about the work, prepared a table for grading each questionnaire as essential, useful but not essential and not essential and also added a separate table for suggestions.
- Among the 22 experts, 16 of them responded back and gave suggestions regarding the work.

Table no.4 – Expert evaluation form

SL.NO	QUESTIONS	DOMAIN	ESSENTIAL	USEFUL BUT NOT ESSENTIAL	NOT ESSENTIAL

Table no.5 – Expert evaluation form

SL.NO	QUESTION NO	COMMENTS	SUGGESTIONS

- ◻ Considering the remarks of the experts, from 44 questions 9 of them were reframed and 1 question was added.
- In Smriti domain-

METHODOLOGY

- All questions were retained.
- In Bhakti Kala-
 - 3 questions were retained the same.
 - Question- 5 was reframed (corrected the grammatical error)
- In Krutajna Domain –
 - 1 question was retained
 - Question number 9 and 11 were reframed (words in the questions were changed)
- In Prajna domain-
 - 4 Questions were retained the same.
 - 1 Question was reframed (grammatical correction).

In domain shuchi

- 4 questions were retained
- The term, ‘ Clipping the nails’ was removed from q. no. 18
- Q. no. 23 was reframed as per expert (grammatical error)

In domain Mahotsaha

- 2 questions were retained
- Q. no 25&26 question was reframed (grammatical correction)

In Daksha domain all questions were retained

In domain Dheera and Samaravikrantayodhina –

- 3 questions were retained
- Q. no. 34 was changed from “Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success” to “What do you do when you observe barriers that block the way to your success?”

METHODOLOGY

In domain suvyavysthithagatigambheerabuddhicheshta all questions were retained

In domain Kalyanabhinivesha 2 questions were retained and 1 question was added as per the expert “ How many days a month you dedicate towards welfare of the society like cleaning neighbourhood?”

- Finally 45 items were taken for further process.

TOOL DEVELOPMENT(13)

1. Pre-Testing of Questions /Pilot Study

- Pre-testing helps to ensure that items are meaningful to the target population before the survey is actually administered.
- Pre-testing eliminates poorly worded items and facilitates revision of phrasing to be maximally understood.
- This step includes the assessment of face validity.
- The prepared Assessment Tool was administered to a population of 18 based on inclusion criteria through the use of Google forms.
- Each domain was considered as an independent scale and these were tested for their reliability using “Cronbach’s Coefficient Alpha”.
- Based on the value of Cronbach’s alpha of entire construct further analysis of the scale was done. An alpha coefficient of 0.70 has often been regarded as an acceptable threshold for reliability.
- A high value for Cronbach’s alpha indicates good internal consistency of the items in the scale.
- Based on pre testing modifications to grammar, word choice, and answer options were made.

3. Sampling and Survey Administration

- The Assessment tool after first step of assessment of reliability and consistency was then administered as a survey through Google forms to 300 participants who fit into the inclusion criteria.

METHODOLOGY

- Assessment tool with 45 items was administered.
- The data was analysed for internal consistency and reliability using Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha.
- The higher the value of the coefficient more is the items that have shared covariance and probably measure the same underlying concept.

4. Item Reduction Analysis

- It is performed to ensure that only concise, practical, and internally coherent items are ultimately incorporated.
- The goal of this phase is to identify items that are not or are the least related to the domain under study for deletion or modification. The deletion is done by-
 - Inter- item correlations.
 - Item- total correlations.
- Inter- item correlations: It examines the extent to which items on a scale are assessing the same content i.e., the extent to which scores on one item are related to scores on all other items in a scale. Item with very low correlations (<0.30) are less desirable & could be a clue for potential deletion from the tentative scale.
- Item- total correlations: It aims at examining the relationship between each item with the total score of scale items.
- Items with very low adjusted item-total correlations (<0.30) are less desirable and could be a cue for potential deletion from the scale.

5. EXTRACTION OF FACTORS

- Factor extraction is the phase in which the optimal number of factors, sometimes called domains, that fit a set of items are determined.

METHODOLOGY

- It is done using Dimension reduction technique and for the current study Factor analysis was the Dimension reduction technique used.
- Factor analysis is a regression model in which observed standardized variables are regressed on unobserved factors. Thus, factor analysis is used to understand the latent structure of a set of items & the extent to which the relationship between the items is internally consistent.
- In the current study Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to reduce the number of variables extracting the essence of the dataset by creating principal components.
- KMO and Bartlett's test was applied. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test evaluates the suitability of data for factor analysis.

Table no.6: KMO measure and interpretation

KMO measure	Interpretation
$KMO \geq 0.90$	Marvelous
$0.80 \leq KMO < 0.90$	Meritorious
$0.70 \leq KMO < 0.80$	Average
$0.60 \leq KMO < 0.70$	Mediocre
$0.50 \leq KMO < 0.60$	Terrible
$KMO < 0.50$	Unacceptable

- For 45 questions in final survey KMO value obtained was 0.868 which indicated acceptable and for each domain above average value.
- In Bartlett's test of Sphericity – "sig" - .000 actually means $p < .005$ which means statistically significant. It was observed in all domains and a total of final 45 questions.

METHODOLOGY

- Varimax rotation was applied to facilitate convergence of items and prevent undue high loading and undue isolated loading of items in any one factor.
- The Principal Component Analysis and varimax rotation was run for the 45 items with 300 samples. The distribution broke into components, out of which 14 components had eigenvalue more than 1 associated with loadings and cross loadings. Further on repeating the test with 28 questions on 500 samples 10 principal components were extracted and Rotation converged in 18 iterations.
- The major output of principal components analysis is the rotated component matrix, also known as the loadings. It contains estimates of the correlations between each of the variables and the estimated components.
- Findings in the form of Rotated Component Matrix, scree plot, were compiled.
- A scree plot which shows how much variation each Principal Component captures from the data is a graph with item numbers on x-axis and eigen values on y-axis. The plot should be a smooth downward curve.
- The scree plot showed 10 components having eigen value above 1.
- The 28 items were distributed among 10 factors which were made into new domains forms a provisional scale.

METHODOLOGY

SCALE EVALUATION

1. Test of Reliability

- Reliability is the degree of consistency exhibited when a measurement is repeated under identical conditions
- Cronbach's alpha was done to check the reliability of the Assessment tool.
- Cronbach's alpha assesses the internal consistency of the tool items, i.e., the degree to which the set of items in the scale co-vary, relative to their sum score.
- Cronbach's alpha was calculated for 45 items with split half and odd and even methods
- Domain wise Cronbach's alpha was calculated for 11 domains
- Pearson's Correlation coefficient was calculated for test – retest reliability by re-administering the questionnaire on the same sample of 300 at different time interval.

2. Tests of Validity

- Construct Validity was measured using tests like Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity

3. Tests of Normality

- Descriptive statistics such as Mean, Std Deviation, Range, Percentiles was calculated
- Each respondent's score (Sum) in the form of Raw score was compiled
- Z score based on the Std deviation and Mean was given for each score
- Cut off scores for the scale was thus calculated using Raw score and Z score.

METHODOLOGY

Table no.7: Draft 1 and 2 of Assessment tool

	Draft 1	Draft 2
Total items	44	45
No: of items revised		9
No: of items added/ deleted		Added- 1
Steps in tool development	Domain identification, Item generation	Item generation and sending to Expert validation

SCALE STANDARDISATION

Methodology

Data Collection

- **Diverse and Representative Sample:** Data was collected from 250 patients of Common Mental Disorders (CMD) and 250 healthy volunteers making a **sample size** of 500 respondents
- **Administer the Scale:** Scale was administered via google forms

Statistical Analysis

- **Descriptive Statistics:** Calculate means, standard deviations, and ranges for the total scale scores and subscale scores to describe the distribution of responses in the sample.
- **Normality Testing:** Assess whether the distribution of scores is normal or introduces any biases (e.g., skewness or kurtosis).

METHODOLOGY

- **Identify Outliers:** Detect any extreme scores that may affect standardization and decide whether to keep or remove them based on reliable reasoning.

6. Norm Development

- **Determine Norms Based on Demographics:** Create normative data for different demographic groups, if relevant. This can include dividing norms by age, gender, or other relevant characteristics.
- **Standard Scoring:** Establish standard scores (e.g., Z-scores or T-scores). Z score calculation was done. This helps to translate raw scores into standardized norms that can be easily interpreted.

7. Establishing Cut-off Scores

- **Clinical and Non-Clinical Ranges:** Define thresholds for various categories such as low, average, and high Sattvabala based on normative data

SAMPLE SIZE ESTIMATION

SAMPLE SIZE ESTIMATION

- Sample size estimation is a critical step in the design of a study, ensuring that the sample is sufficiently large to detect effects and draw valid conclusions while considering various factors such as the desired statistical power, effect size, significance level, and variability in the data.
- Sample size estimation for **scale validation and standardization** is essential to ensure that the results are statistically valid and reliable. The process involves several key steps and considerations that are specific to the nature of scale development, validation, and standardization.
- Rule of Thumb: A common guideline is to have at least 5 to 10 participants per item in the scale. [$n \geq \text{Number of items} \times 5 \text{ or } 10$]
- For example, if your scale has 20 items, you would need a minimum sample size of 100 (5 participants per item) to 200 (10 participants per item) for your factor analysis.
- Generally, you will need around 300 respondents as a minimum to stabilize reliability estimates reliably, especially for calculating Cronbach's alpha. Larger samples (500-1000) yield more confidence in the generalizability of the reliability estimates.
- Considering rule of thumb guidelines, tests of reliability and previous studies a final sample size of 800, ie, 300 respondents for validation and 500 respondents for standardization was finalized.
- Sample size was decided based on previous scale validation studies, Best Practices for Developing and Validating Scales for Health, Social, and Behavioral Research: A Primer and finalized as 300 healthy volunteers for validation and 500 volunteers irrespective of their health status for standardization.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Pretesting phase Observations and Results

1. Face Validity - Face validity is a subjective assessment of whether a test or scale appears to measure what it's supposed to. It's a quick and easy way to check if a measure seems useful, but it's not a reliable indicator of actual validity.
 - a. Expert evaluation – Experts from the field of Manovigyan, Psychology, English language were consulted, to evaluate the 44 item questionnaire on Sattvabala, grading each item of each domain under Essential, Useful but not essential and Not Essential. Based on the evaluation, the following questions were modified. One question was added under the domain ‘ Kalyanabhinivesha’.
 - Among the 22 experts, 16 of them responded back and gave suggestions regarding the work.
 - 1 Question was reframed (grammatical correction).
 - In domain shuchi
 - 4 questions were retained
 - The term, ‘ Clipping the nails’ was removed from q. no. 18
 - Q. no. 23 was reframed as per expert (grammatical error)
 - In domain Mahotsaha
 - 2 questions were retained
 - Q. no 25&26 question was reframed (grammatical correction)
 - In Daksha domain all questions were retained
 - In domain Dheera and Samaravikrantayodhina –

- 3 questions were retained
 - Q. no. 34 was changed from “Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success” to “What do you do when you observe barriers that block the way to your success?”
 - In domain suvyavysthithagatigambheerabuddhicheshta all questions were retained
 - In domain Kalyanabhinivesha 2 questions were retained and 1 question was added as per the expert “ How many days a month you dedicate towards welfare of the society like cleaning neighbourhood?”
 - Finally 45 items were taken for further process.
- b. Results of Pilot Test conducted on 18 healthy volunteers

Pilot study was reviewed for information about item content, including clarity and readability as well as for any errors in the administration procedures.

STEP 1 – First Analysis in 18 participants with items

Table no 8 -Observation based on Age groups		
	Frequency	Percent
18-20	2	11.1
21-30	8	44.4
31-40	8	44.4
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants 11.1% belonged to 18-20 years of age, 44.4% between 21-30 years of age, 44.4% between 31-40 years of age.

Table No 9- Observation based on Male, Female		
	Frequency	Percent
Male	10	55.6
Female	8	44.4
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants 55.6% were Males and 44.4% were Females.

Table No 10- Observation based on Hindu,Christian, Muslim,Others		
	Frequency	Percent
Hindu	17	94.4
Others	1	5.6
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants 94.4% were Hindus and 5.6% were Others.

Table No 11 -Observation based on Education Completed		
	Frequency	Percent
PreUniversity	1	5.6
Undergraduation	12	66.7
Postgraduation	5	27.8
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants 5.6% completed
Pre-University education, 66.7% were graduates and 27.8% were Post graduates.

Table number 12 - Observation based on Occupation		
	Frequency	Percent
Employed	9	50.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Unemployed	9	50.0
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants 50% were employed and 50 % unemployed.

	Frequency	Percent
Lower middle class	5	27.8
middle class	2	11.1
upper middle class	11	61.1
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants 27.8% were from Lower middle class, 11.1% belonged to middle class and 61.1% from upper middle class.

	Frequency	Percent
Married	8	44.4
Unmarried	10	55.6
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 44.4% reported married and 55.6% reported to be unmarried.

	Frequency	Percent
Karnataka	4	22.2
Out of Karnataka	14	77.8
Total	18	100.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Among 18 participants, 22.2% belonged to Karnataka and 77.8% from Outside Karnataka.

Table number 16-

1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I forget many times	2	11.1
b. Sometimes I forget	10	55.6
c. I remember to carry everything required	6	33.3
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 11.1% reported to be forgetting many times, 55.6% reported forgetting sometimes and 33.3% reported to be carrying everything required.

Table #17 -

2. How often do you recheck to ensure the work is done?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Rechecking things many times is one of my habits	2	11.1
b. A few times, maybe	10	55.6
c. I recheck once	6	33.3
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 11.1% reported to be rechecking multiple times, 55.6% reported rechecking a few times and 33.3% reported one time recheck.

Table #18 -

3. How often do you need help remembering important dates, events, and names of people?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Yes, every time I need reminders	1	5.6
b. Yes, Sometimes	11	61.1
c. Very rarely I may need help	6	33.3

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Total	18	100.0
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Among 18 participants, 5.6% reported in need for reminder everytime, 61.1% reported needing reminder sometimes and 33.3% reported not in need of any help.

Table number 19-

4. How often do you need tricks and techniques for memory? For eg: mnemonics, sing it out, etc.		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Tricks and techniques do not work for me	1	5.6
b. Some work, some do not.	14	77.8
c. I rarely need tricks and techniques.	3	16.7
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 5.6% reported Tricks and techniques do not work, 77.8% reported Some work, some do not, 16.7% reported they rarely need tricks and techniques

Table #20 -

5. How often do you engage in activities other than your academic or professional interests?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Very Rarely, Unless forced	1	5.6
b. Sometimes when I find them interesting	7	38.9
c. I like to try out new things	10	55.6
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 5.6% reported Very Rarely, Unless forced, 38.9% reported Sometimes when I find them interesting, and 55.6% reported to like to try out new things.

Table #21 -

6. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?
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OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Frequency	Percent
b. I can sustain interest with efforts	2	11.1
c. I can easily maintain my interest	16	88.9
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 11.1% reported to sustain interest with efforts and 88.9% can easily maintain my interest.

Table #22 -

7. Is it common for you to only be interested in things you are familiar with?		
For eg: An engineer may be willing to write movie reviews but unwilling to learn Bharatanatyam dance		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	2	11.1
b. Sometimes	14	77.8
c. Never	2	11.1
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 11.1% reported Most of the time, 77.8% reported Sometimes, 11.1% reported Never.

Table #23 -

8. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I need encouraging words from time to time	1	5.6
b. I may sometimes need	7	38.9
c. I can stay motivated without much help	10	55.6
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 5.6% reported needing encouraging words from time to time, 38.9% reported may sometimes need, 55.6% can stay motivated without much help.

Table #24 -

9.Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I rarely express gratitude	2	11.1
b. Yes, sometimes	8	44.4
c. I regularly thank my family for their contributions	8	44.4
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 11.1% reported they rarely express gratitude, 44.4% reported sometimes, and 44.4% reported they regularly thank my family for their contributions

Table #25 -

10.Do you feel that it is the parents/spouse's responsibility to take care of the family?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Yes, It is their responsibility	1	5.6
b. As a family caregiver, I am more responsible	2	11.1
c. No, all have shared responsibilities	15	83.3
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 5.6% reported It is their responsibility, 11.1% reported As a family caregiver, I am more responsible, and 83.3% opined all have shared responsibilities.

Table #26 -

11. Does your family ever remind you to say thanks for the favors received?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. Yes, Sometimes	5	27.8
c. No, I usually appreciate the favors received.	13	72.2
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 27.8% reported Sometimes, 72.2% reported to usually appreciate the favors received.

Table #27 -

11. Does your family ever remind you to say thanks for the favors received?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. Yes, Sometimes	5	27.8
c. No, I usually appreciate the favors received.	13	72.2
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 27.8% reported Sometimes, 72.2% reported to usually appreciate the favors received.

Table #28 -

13. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. Sometimes	8	44.4
c. Never	10	55.6
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 44.4% reported sometimes and 55.6% reported never.

Table #29 -

14. Have you anytime faced problems because of your absent-minded/ negligent behavior?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Yes, many times	2	11.1
b. Yes, sometimes	9	50.0
c. I am careful	7	38.9
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 11.1% reported Yes, many times, 50% Yes, sometimes and 38.9% reported careful.

Table #30-

15. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Multitasking is very difficult for me and I make mistakes	1	5.6
b. I sometimes make mistakes	12	66.7
c. Usually, I can manage multitasking	5	27.8
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 5.6% reported Multitasking is very difficult, 66.7% reported I sometimes make mistakes, 27.8% Usually, I can manage multitasking.

Table number 31 -

16. How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Very likely	3	16.7
b. Sometimes	7	38.9
c. Unlikely	8	44.4
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 16.7% reported Very likely, 38.9% reported Sometimes, 44.4% reported unlikely.

Table #32 -

17. Can you wear the same clothes for two straight days?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Yes, I can	7	38.9
b. Sometimes maybe	6	33.3
c. No, I cant	5	27.8
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 38.9% reported Yes, I can, 33.3 % reported Sometimes maybe, 27.8% reported No, I cant.

Table #33 -

18. Can you skip daily routines like washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. Sometimes	11	61.1
c. No, I cant	7	38.9
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants,61.1% reported Sometimes, 38.9% reported No, I cant

Table no 34 -

19.On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. It is difficult to change my habits most of the times.	1	5.6
b. Sometimes, maybe	10	55.6
c. I am flexible to modifications.	7	38.9
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 5.6% reported It is difficult to change my habits most of the times, 55.6% sometimes and 38.9% reported I am flexible to modifications.

Table #35 -

Among 18 participants, 5.6% reported Several times, 38.9% reported Sometimes and 55.6% reported very rarely.

Table number 36 -

21.Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. My habits are hard to change	1	5.6
b. Sometimes, maybe	9	50.0
c. I can modify it accordingly	8	44.4
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 5.6% reported My habits are hard to change, 50% reported Sometimes, maybe, 44.4% I can modify it accordingly.

Table #37 -

22.How often have you cried, shouted, or taken your anger out of place?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I usually can't control my feelings	3	16.7
b. Sometimes I can	9	50.0
c. I can identify my feelings and control them	6	33.3
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 16.7% reported I usually can't control my feelings, 50% reported Sometimes I can, 33.3 % I can identify my feelings and control them

Table #38 -

23.Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I often express my feelings too much/too little	2	11.1

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

b. Sometimes	8	44.4
c. I am aware of how much to express	8	44.4
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 11.1% reported I often express my feelings too much/too little, 44.4% reported Sometimes, 44.4% reported I am aware of how much to express.

Table Number 39-

24. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. Sometimes, Maybe	10	55.6
c. I maintain the same energy till the completion.	8	44.4
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 55.6% reported Sometimes, 44.4% reported maintain the same energy till the completion.

Table number 40 -

25. Did you ever change courses/jobs because it got boring?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Yes, Many times	1	5.6
b. Yes, Sometimes	7	38.9
c. No, I continue even if it gets boring.	10	55.6
Total	18	100.0

Among 18 participants, 5.6% reported Many times, 38.6 % reported Sometimes, 55.6% reported No.

Table #41 -

26. Do you find your enthusiasm reduces as the day progresses?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. Sometimes	13	72.2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

c. Never	5	27.8
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 72.2% reported sometimes 27.8% reported never.

Table #42 -

27.How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. Sometimes, Even if I don't receive it, can manage.	9	50.0
c. Rewards do not affect my energy to do work.	9	50.0
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 50% reported sometimes, even if I don't receive it can manage and 50% reported rewards do not affect my energy to do work.

Table #43 -

28.How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. I take help in difficult situations	13	72.2
c. I can handle tough situations on my own	5	27.8
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 72.2% reported I take help in difficult situations 27.8% reported I can handle tough situations on my own.

table number 44 -

29. Do you think your educational qualification/ development of skills has added to your work efficiency?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. No, I do not think so	1	5.6
b. Sometimes, maybe	3	16.7

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

c. Yes, it has	14	77.8
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 5.6% reported no I do not think so 16.7% reported sometimes, may be, 77.8% reported yes, it has.

Table #45 -

30. Have you not received appreciation/awards/rewards for your skills in managing your duties?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	4	22.2
b. Sometimes	14	77.8
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 22.2% reported most of the times 77.8% reported sometimes

Table #46 -

31. Do you believe in living a peaceful life without taking risks?		
	Frequency	Percent
a.		
b. Sometimes, maybe	6	33.3
c. I can take risks and manage	12	66.7
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants, 33.3% reported sometimes, may be 66.7% reported I can take risks and manage.

Table #47 -

32. Would you invest your hard-earned money and time in a new venture?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. I may take a chance	10	55.6
c. Yes, I would definitely	8	44.4
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants, 55.6% reported I may take a chance. 44.4% reported yes I would definitely.

Table #48 -

33.Do you bounce back after a failure?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. Yes, with support from family	6	33.3
c. Yes, I can bounce back	12	66.7
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 33.3% reported yes with the support from family. 66.7% reported yes I can bounce back.

Table #49 -

34.Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I avoid the barriers	5	27.8
b. I try to cross them with support	4	22.2
c. I face them confidently	9	50.0
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 27.8% reported I avoid the barriers. 22.2% reported I try to cross them with support. 50% reported I face them confidently.

Table number 50 -

35.How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Very likely	1	5.6
b. Rarely	14	77.8
c. Unlikely	3	16.7
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 5.6% reported very likely 77.8% reported rarely 16.7% reported unlikely.

Table #51 -

36. Do you consider yourself an emotionally sensitive person in tough situations?
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OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	3	16.7
b. Sometimes, maybe	12	66.7
c. No, I am strong emotionally	3	16.7
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 16.7% reported most of the time, 66.7% reported sometimes, maybe, 16.7% reported no I am strong emotionally.

Table #52 -

37.Do you find it easy to recover emotionally after a crisis?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. I take some time to recover completely	15	83.3
c. I can easily recover from a crisis	3	16.7
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants, 83.8% reported I can take some time to recover completely and one 16.7% reported I can easily recover from a crisis

Table #53 -

38.Do you consider the future consequences when you are doing work?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. No, I live in the present	1	5.6
b. Sometimes I consider	10	55.6
c. Always I am concerned about the future	7	38.9
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 5.6% reported no I live in the present. 55.6% reported sometimes I consider 38.9% reported always I am concerned about future.

Table #54 -

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

39.Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	2	11.1
b. Sometimes	11	61.1
c. Never	5	27.8
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 11.1% reported most of the times, 61.1% reported Sometimes and 27.8% reported never.

Table #55 -

40. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Mostly it does not yield the best results	1	5.6
b. Sometimes	9	50.0
c. Maximum occasions yield the best results	8	44.4
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 5.6% reported mostly it does not yield best results and 50% reported sometimes and 44.4% reported maximum occasion yields the best results.

Table #56 -

41.Do you procrastinate on your work?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Many times,	4	22.2
b. Sometimes	13	72.2
c. I do not	1	5.6
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 22.2% reported many times 72.2% reported sometimes and 5.6% reported I do not.

Table #57 -

42.Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Many times	0	0
b. Sometimes	10	55.6
c. Never	8	44.4
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 55.6% reported sometimes and four four point four percent reported never.

Table #58 -

43.What is the likelihood of you considering your parents'/spouse's/children's decisions over your own?		
	Frequency	Percent
b. Sometimes	13	72.2
c. Always	5	27.8
Total	18	100.0

Out of the 18 participants, 72.2% reported sometimes and 27.8% reported always.

Table #59 -

44.Regardless of who is at fault, do you apologize to your parents/spouse/children?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I do not	2	11.1
b. Sometimes, if forced	3	16.7
c. I apologize	13	72.2
Total	18	100.0

Out of the 18 participants 11.1% reported I do not 16.7% reported sometimes if forced and 72.2% reported I apologise.

Table number 60 -

45.How many days a month you dedicate towards welfare of the society like cleaning neighbourhood?		
	Frequency	Percent

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

less than a day.	8	44.4
. 1-3 days	10	55.6
Total	18	100.0

Out of 18 participants 44.4% reported less than a day and 55.6% reported one to three days.

Table no.61: Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases		18	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	18	100.0

18 cases are in analysis due to no missing values. All the respondents were comfortable in answering the questions.

- The questions and options given were easy to understand
- The intended meaning of the construct was comprehensible

STEP 2 - Second analysis in 300 subjects (N=300) with 45 items

The questionnaire after the 1st step of assessment of reliability and consistency was then applied to survey on 300 subjects on the basis of inclusion criteria. 45 items were administered.

Table no.62: Age Group Wise Distribution

	Frequency	Percent
18-20	35	11.7
21-25	132	44.0
26-30	65	21.7
31-35	28	9.3
36-40	15	5.0
41-45	7	2.3
46-50	5	1.7
51-55	6	2.0
55-60	7	2.3
Total	300	100.0

Among 300 participants 11.7% belonged to 18-20 years of age, 44% between 21-25 years of age, 21.7% between 26-30 years of age, 9.3% 31-35 years of age, 5% years of 36-40 of age 2.3% of 41-45 years of age, 1.7% of 46-50 years of age, 2% of 51-55 years of age, 2.3% of 55 -60 years of age.

Table no.63: Gender Wise Distribution

	Frequency	Percent
Male	80	26.7
Female	220	73.3
Total	300	100.0

Among 300 participants 26.7% were males and 73.3% were females.

Table no.64: Religion- wise distribution

	Frequency	Percent
Hindu	245	81.7
Christian	22	7.3
Muslim	18	6.0
Others	15	5.0
Total	300	100.0

Among 300 participants, 81.7% were Hindus, 7.3% were Christians and 0.8 % were Muslims.

Table no.65: Observation on Marital Status

	Frequency	Percent
Married	91	30.3
Unmarried	209	69.7
Total	300	100.0

Among 300 participants, 30% were married, 69.7% were unmarried, none reported separated.

Table no.66: Observation on Education

	Frequency	Percent
Uneducated	1	.3
Primary	5	1.7
Secondary	39	13.0
Pre-University	166	55.3
Graduation	89	29.7
Total	300	100.0

Among 300 participants, 0.3% uneducated, 1.7% had primary education, 13% had secondary education, 55.3 % had Pre university education, 29.7 % had completed under graduation and none reported completing post-graduation.

Table no.67: Observation on Occupation

		Frequency	Percent
	Employed	129	43.0
	Unemployed	171	57.0
	Total	300	100.0

Among 300 participants, 43% were employed and 57% unemployed.

Table no.68: Observation on Socio-economic Status

		Frequency	Percent
	Lower Middle Class	11	3.7
	Middle Class	267	89.0
	Upper Class	22	7.3
	Total	300	100.0

Among 300 participants, 3.7% of them belong to lower middle class, 89% are from middle class and 7.3% belongs to upper socio-economic status.

Table no.69: Observation on Place

		Frequency	Percent
	Karnataka	156	52.0
	Out of Karnataka	144	48.0
	Total	300	100.0

Among 300 participants, 52% belonged to Karnataka and 48% were from non-Karnataka residents.

Table No70: 1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?

		Frequency	Percent
	I forget many times	22	7.3
	Sometimes I forget	172	57.3
	I remember to carry everything required	106	35.3
	Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects, 7.3% reported to being forgetful many times, 57.3% report they sometimes forget to carry necessary tools and 35.3% reported to remember to carry everything required.

Table no.71: 2. How often do you recheck to ensure the work is done?

	Frequency	Percent
Rechecking things many times is one of my habits	64	21.3
A few times, maybe	137	45.7
I recheck once	99	33.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 21.3 % reported multiple rechecking, 45.7% reported rechecking a few times, and 33% reported rechecking once.

Table 72 : 3. How often do you need help remembering important dates, events, and names of people?

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Frequency	Percent
Yes, every time I need reminders	46	15.3
Yes, Sometimes	147	49.0
Very rarely I may need help	107	35.7
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects, 15.3 % reported they need timely reminders, 49% reported they sometimes need reminder, 35.7% reported very rare need of help.

Table74

4. How often do you need tricks and techniques for memory? For eg: mnemonics, sing it out, etc.		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Tricks and techniques do not work for me	16	5.3
b. Some work, some do not.	153	51
c. I rarely need tricks and techniques.	131	43.7
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 5.3% reported tricks and techniques do not work for me, 51% reported some work and some don't and four 3.7% reported they rarely need tricks and techniques.

Table75 5. How often do you perform your daily activities (professional/personal) with complete interest?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Very Rarely, unless forced	16	5.3
b. Sometimes when I find them interesting	153	51.0
c. I like to try out new things	131	43.7
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects, 5.3% reported to performing daily activities without complete interest, 51% report to try out on things only when they find them interesting, 43.7% reported to be interested to try out new things.

Table 76: 6. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I usually struggle to keep up my interest	75	25.0
b. I can sustain interest with efforts	125	41.7
c. I can easily maintain my interest	100	33.3

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Total	300	100.0
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Out of 300 subjects, 25% reported to be struggling to keep up interest, 41.7% reported to maintaining interest with efforts, 33.3% reported to maintain interest without any aid.

Table 77. Is it common for you to only be interested in things you are familiar with?

For eg: doctors who are willing to write movie reviews but unwilling to learn computer coding.

	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	79	26.3
b. Sometimes	169	56.3
c. Never	52	17.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects, 26.3% reported to be interested in things they are familiar with only, when 56.3% reported sometimes and 17.3% reported never.

Table78

8. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task?

(For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)

	Frequency	Percent
a. I need encouraging words from time to time	53	17.7
b. I may sometimes need	139	46.3
c. I can stay motivated without much help	108	36.0
Total	300	100.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Out of 300 subjects, 17.7% reported needing frequent encouragement, when 46.3% reported they may sometimes need it, 36% reported they remain motivated even when they don't receive appreciations.

Table 79

9. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse/friends/neighbours?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I rarely express gratitude	36	12.0
b. Yes, Sometime	119	39.7
c. I regularly thank my family for their contributions	145	48.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects, 12% reported they rarely express gratitude, 39.7% express sometimes and 48.3% regularly express gratitude.

Table 80

10. Do you feel that it is the parents/spouse's responsibility to take care of the family?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Yes, It is their responsibility	23	7.7
b. As a family caregiver, I am more responsible	46	15.3
c. No, all have shared responsibilities	231	77.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects, 7.7% agreed it was their responsibility, 15.3 % felt they are more responsible

as a family caregiver and 77% felt all had equal responsibility.

Table 81-

11. Does your family ever remind you to appreciate for the favors received?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Yes, Very often	27	9.0
b. Yes, Sometimes	102	34.0
c. No, I usually appreciate the favors received.	171	57.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 9% reported yes very often. 34% reported yes. And 57% reported no, I usually appreciate the favours received.

Table 82

12. How often do you find yourself distracted/ confused in your daily life?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	82	27.3
b. Sometimes	199	66.3
c. Never	19	6.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 27 .3% reported most of the time, 66 .3% reported sometimes and 6.3% reported never.

Table 83

13. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	38	12.7
b. Sometimes	144	48.0
c. Never	118	39.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of the 300 subject, 12.7% reported most of the time 48% reported sometimes and 39.3% reported never.

Table 84

14. Have you ever faced problems due of your absent-minded/ negligent behavior?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Yes, many times	42	14.0
b. Yes, sometimes	171	57.0
c. I am careful	87	29.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 14% reported many times, 57% reported yes sometimes and 29% reported I am careful.

Table 85

15. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Multitasking is very difficult for me and I make mistakes	39	13.0
b. I sometimes make mistakes	171	57.0
c. Usually, I can manage multitasking	90	30.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 13% reported multitasking is very difficult, 57% reported I sometimes make mistakes and 30% reported usually I can manage multitasking.

Table 86

16. How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Very likely	40	13.3
b. Sometimes	127	42.3
c. Unlikely	133	44.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 13.3 percent reported very likely, four two point three percent reported sometimes and four four point three percent reported unlikely.

Table 87

17. Do you wear the same clothes for two straight days?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Yes, I can	59	19.7

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

b. Sometimes maybe	93	31.0
c. No, I cant	148	49.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 19.7% reported yes, I can. 31.0% reported sometimes may be and 49.3% reported no I can't.

Table 88

18. Do you skip daily routines like washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	13	4.3
b. Sometimes	72	24.0
c. No, I cant	215	71.7
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 4.3% reported most of their time, 24% reported sometimes and 71.7% reported no, I can't.

Table 89

19. On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. It is difficult to change my habits most of the times.	50	16.7
b. Sometimes, maybe	139	46.3
c. I am flexible to modifications.	111	37.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Total	300	100.0
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Out of 300 subjects 16.7% reported it is difficult to change my habits 46.3% percent reported sometimes may be and 37% reported I am flexible to modifications.

Table 90

20. Have you been blamed for talking rudely by your family?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Several times	54	18.0
b. Sometimes	110	36.7
c. Very rarely	136	45.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 18% reported several times 36.7% reported sometimes and 45.3% percent reported very rarely.

Table 91

21. Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. My habits are hard to change	20	6.7
b. Sometimes, maybe	142	47.3
c. I can modify it accordingly	138	46.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 6. 7% reported my habits are hard to change 47 .3% reported sometimes and 46% reported I can modify accordingly.

Table 92

22. How often do you express your emotions inappropriately?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	37	12.3
b. Sometimes	203	67.7
c. Never	60	20.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 12.3% reported most of their time, 67.7% reported sometimes and 20% reported never.

Table 93

23. Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family/friends/colleagues?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I often express my feelings too much/too little	72	24.0
b. Sometimes	120	40.0
c. I am aware of how much to express	108	36.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 subjects 24% reported I often express my feelings too much or too little 40% reported sometimes and 36% reported I am aware of how much I have to express.

Table 94

24. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. My enthusiasm reduces very fast	55	18.3
b. Sometimes, Maybe	172	57.3
c. I maintain the same energy till the completion.	73	24.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 respondents 18.3% reported my enthusiasm reduces very fast 57.3% reported sometimes and 24.3% reported I maintain the same energy.

Table 95

25. Did you ever quit/change jobs because it got boring?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Yes, Many times	25	8.3
b. Yes, Sometimes	122	40.7
c. No, I continue even if it gets boring.	153	51.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 respondents 8.3 percent reported yes many times, 40.7% reported yes sometimes and 51% reported no.

Table 96

26. Do you find your enthusiasm reducing as the day progresses?			
		Frequency	Percent
	a. Most of the time	53	17.7
	b. Sometimes	192	64.0
	c. Never	55	18.3
	Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 respondents 17.7% reported most of the Times, 64% reported sometimes and 18.3% reported never.

Table 97

27. How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?			
		Frequency	Percent
a. I frequently need them, it helps me keep going.		48	16.0
b. Sometimes, Even if I don't receive it, can manage.		174	58.0
c. Rewards do not affect my energy to do work.		78	26.0
Total		300	100.0

Out of 300 respondents 16% reported I frequently need rewards and cheers, 58% reported sometimes I may need, 26% reported rewards do not affect my energy to do

 work
Table 98

28. How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. No, I avoid myself from difficult situations	22	7.3
b. I take help in difficult situations	159	53.0
c. I can handle tough situations on my own	119	39.7
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 respondents 7.3% responded no I avoid myself from difficult situations ,53% reported I take help in difficult situations and 39.7% reported I can handle tough situations on my own.

Table 99

29. Do you think your educational qualification/ development of skills has added to your work efficiency?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. No, I do not think so	28	9.3
b. Sometimes, Maybe	97	32.3
c. Yes, it has	175	58.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 respondents, 9.3 percent reported no I do not think so, 32.3% reported sometimes and 58.3% reported yes it has.

Table 100

30. Have you not received appreciation/awards/rewards for your skills in managing your duties?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	44	14.7
b. Sometimes	199	66.3
c. Never	57	19.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 14.7% reported most of the Times 66.3% reported sometimes and 19% reported never.

Table 101

31. Do you believe in living a peaceful life without taking risks?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Yes, I avoid risk	50	16.7
b. Sometimes, maybe	131	43.7
c. I can take risks and manage	119	39.7
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants, 16.7% reported Yes, I avoid risk 43.7% reported sometimes and 39.7% reported I can take risk and manage.

Table 102

32. Do you invest your hard-earned money and time in a new venture?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Never	46	15.3
b. I may take a chance	184	61.3
c. Yes, I would definitely	70	23.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 15.3% reported never, 61.3% reported I may take a chance and 23.3% reported yes I would definitely.

Table 103

33. Do you bounce back after a failure?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Maybe, with support from family	34	11.3
b. Yes, with support from family	115	38.3
c. Yes, I can bounce back	151	50.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 11.3% reported may be with support from family, 38.3% reported yes with support from family and 50.3% reported yes I can bounce back.

Table 104

34. What do you do when you observe barriers that block the way to your success?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I avoid the barriers	25	8.3
b. I try to cross them with support	136	45.3
c. I face them confidently	139	46.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 8.3% reported I avoid the barriers,45.3% reported I try to cross them with support and 46.3% reported I face them confidently.

Table 105

35. How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Very likely	67	22.3
b. Rarely	178	59.3
c. Unlikely	55	18.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 22.3% reported very likely, 59.3% reported rarely and 18.3% reported unlikely.

Table 106

36. Are you emotionally sensitive like sad/anxious/irritable/angry towards tough situations		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	98	32.7
b. Sometimes, maybe	165	55.0
c. No, I am strong emotionally	37	12.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 32.7% reported most of the Times, 55% reported sometimes and 12.3% reported no I am strong emotionally

Table 107

37. Do you find it easy to recover emotionally after a crisis?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. No, I may or may not recover completely after a crisis	26	8.7
b. I take some time to recover completely	207	69.0
c. I can easily recover from a crisis	67	22.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 8.7% reported no I may not recover from a crisis, 69% reported I take time to recover completely and 22.3% reported I can easily recover from the crisis.

Table 108

38. Are you concerned about the future consequence while working?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. No, I live in the present	27	9.0
b. Sometimes I consider	166	55.3
c. Always I am concerned about the future	107	35.7
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 9% reported no I live in the present ,55.3% reported sometimes I consider and 35.7% reported I am always concerned about the future.

Table 108

39. Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	39	13.0
b. Sometimes	149	49.7
c. Never	112	37.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 13% reported most of the times, 49.7% reported sometimes and 37.3% reported never.

Table 109

40. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Mostly it does not yield the best results	31	10.3
b. Sometimes	132	44.0
c. Maximum occasions yield the best results	137	45.7
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants, 10.3% reported mostly it doesn't yield the best result, 44% reported sometimes and 45.7% reported maximum occasion yields the best results.

Table 110

41. Do you procrastinate on your work?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Many times,	70	23.3
b. Sometimes	180	60.0
c. I do not	50	16.7
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 23.3% reported many times 60% reported sometimes and 16.7% reported I do not.

Table 111

42. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Most of the time	44	14.7
b. Sometimes	153	51.0
c. Never	103	34.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 14.7% reported most of the Times, 51% reported sometimes and 34.3% reported never.

Table 112

43. Do you consider your parents'/spouse's/children's suggestions over your own during major decisions?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. Rarely	38	12.7
b. Sometimes	163	54.3
c. Always	99	33.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 12.7% reported rarely 54.3% reported sometimes and 33% reported always.

Table 113

44. Regardless of who is at fault, do you apologize to your parents/spouse/children?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. I do not	39	13.0
b. Sometimes, if forced	71	23.7
c. I apologize	190	63.3
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 13% reported I do not, 23.7% reported sometimes if forced and 63.3% reported I apologise.

Table 114

45. How many days a month you dedicate towards welfare of the society like cleaning neighbourhood?		
	Frequency	Percent
a. less than a day.	279	93.0
c. 3-5 days	21	7.0
Total	300	100.0

Out of 300 participants 93% reported they spend less than a day in a month and 7% reported three to five days in a month.

Table 115 - Case Processing Summary of 2nd Analysis

		N	%
Cases		300	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	0.0
	Total	300	100.0

300 cases are in analysis due to no missing values. All the respondents were comfortable in answering the questions.

Domainwise internal reliability and suitability of data for factor analysis

DOMAIN 1 – SMRITI – Table number 116

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.417	4

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.602
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	46.645
	df	6
	Sig.	.000

DOMAIN 2 – BHAKTI- Table number 117

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.591	4

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.658
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	121.640
	df	6
	Sig.	.000

DOMAIN 3- KRUTAJNA – Table number 118

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.352	3

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.531
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	27.710
	df	3

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Sig.	.000
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DOMAIN 4 – PRAJNA- Table number 119

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.693	5

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.754
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	238.828
	df
	10
	Sig.
	.000

DOMAIN 5 – SHUCHI – Table number 120

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.558	7

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.663
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	152.146
	df
	21
	Sig.
	.000

DOMAIN 6 – MAHOTSAHA – Table number 121

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.564	4

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.633
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	119.298
	df
	6

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Sig.	.000
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DOMAIN 7 – DAKSHA- Table #122

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.441	3

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.549
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	df
	Sig.
	43.123
	3
	.000

DOMAIN 8- DHEERA AND SAMARAVIKRANTAYODHI- Table #123

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.492	4

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.559
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	df
	Sig.
	90.775
	6
	.000

DOMAIN 9 – TYAKTAVISHADA- Table #124

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.570	3

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.592
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	85.696

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

df	3
Sig.	.000

**DOMAIN 10- SUVYAVASTHITHAGATI&GAMBHEERABUDDHI CHESHTA-
Table #125**

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.463	5

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.645
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	80.211
	df
	10
	Sig.
	.000

DOMAIN 11- KALYANABHINIVESHA- Table #126

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.17	3

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.490
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	5.987
	df
	3
	Sig.
	.112

ENTIRE CONSTRUCT**Table no.127: Internal consistency for 300 subjects for the Entire Construct**

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.868	45

The Internal consistency of items was analyzed for the each domain and the entire construct Sattvabala , with 45 items. Although the statistical tests showed lesser Cronbach's alpha and minimal KMO values for each domain, **the value of Cronbach's alpha was 0.868 for 45 items, i.e, entire construct. As it is considered being excellent.** Hence the overall scale showed good internal consistency.

Table no.128: KMO & Bartlett's test for the entire construct of 45 items

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.820
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	df
	Sig.
	3016.236
	990
	.000

KMO value was 0.820 (meritorious) and Bartlett's test showed a value of 0.000 which indicates statistical significance for $p < 0.005$ (correlation matrix is sufficient to perform factor analysis). Therefore, this construct is qualified for PCA.

The KMO measure of sampling adequacy is a test used to determine if it is suitable to apply factor analysis to a given dataset. It helps us assess whether the data we have is appropriate

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

for conducting factor analysis. KMO values greater than .8 is good for a questionnaire.

0.895 IS MERITORIOUS

BARTLETTE TEST IS SGNIFICANT – which means the 45 variables have got correlation with each other.

STEP 3- Factor analysis – Exploratory Factor Analysis

Factor extraction is the process of identifying the underlying structure in a set of variables by reducing the data into a smaller number of factors that explain most of the variance.

Method used was- Principal Component Analysis –

Popular rule of thumb is Eigenvalue more than 1

- Dimension reduction test (Principal component analysis) was done at this stage to reduce the larger set of variables into smaller ones called principal components.
- Communalities of the variables (< 0.4 does not contribute much) indicated that the variables are well represented in the common space.

Table #129

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?	1.000	.627
2.How often do you recheck to ensure the work is done?	1.000	.597

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

3. How often do you need help remembering important dates, events, and names of people?	1.000	.566
4. How often do you need tricks and techniques for memory? For eg: mnemonics, sing it out, etc.	1.000	.549
5. How often do you perform your daily activities (professional/personal) with complete interest?	1.000	.559
6. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?	1.000	.573
7. Is it common for you to only be interested in things you are familiar with? For eg: doctors who are willing to write movie reviews but unwilling to learn computer coding.	1.000	.550
8. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)	1.000	.495

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

9. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse/friends/neighbours?	1.000	.567
10. Do you feel that it is the parents/spouse's responsibility to take care of the family?	1.000	.579
11. Does your family ever remind you to appreciate for the favors received?	1.000	.588
12. How often do you find yourself distracted/ confused in your daily life?	1.000	.570
13. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?	1.000	.569
14. Have you ever faced problems due of your absent-minded/ negligent behavior?	1.000	.581
15. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?	1.000	.553
16. How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?	1.000	.461

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

17. Do you wear the same clothes for two straight days?	1.000	.651
18. Do you skip daily routines like washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?	1.000	.528
19. On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?	1.000	.434
20. Have you been blamed for talking rudely by your family?	1.000	.617
21. Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?	1.000	.513
22. How often do you express your emotions inappropriately?	1.000	.623
23. Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family/friends/colleagues?	1.000	.554
24. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?	1.000	.563

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

25. Did you ever quit/change jobs because it got boring?	1.000	.520
26. Do you find your enthusiasm reducing as the day progresses?	1.000	.573
27. How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?	1.000	.654
28. How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?	1.000	.572
29. Do you think your educational qualification/ development of skills has added to your work efficiency?	1.000	.612
30. Have you not received appreciation/awards/rewards for your skills in managing your duties?	1.000	.541
31. Do you believe in living a peaceful life without taking risks?	1.000	.645
32. Do you invest your hard-earned money and time in a new venture?	1.000	.623
33. Do you bounce back after a failure?	1.000	.522
34. What do you do when you observe barriers that block the way to your success?	1.000	.593

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

35. How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?	1.000	.565
36. Are you emotionally sensitive like sad/anxious/irritable/angry towards tough situations	1.000	.583
37. Do you find it easy to recover emotionally after a crisis?	1.000	.673
38. Are you concerned about the future consequence while working?	1.000	.632
39. Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?	1.000	.596
40. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?	1.000	.569
41. Do you procrastinate on your work?	1.000	.535
42. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?	1.000	.662
43. Do you consider your parents'/spouse's/children's suggestions over your own during major decisions?	1.000	.618
44. Regardless of who is at fault, do you apologize to your parents/spouse/children?	1.000	.597

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

45. How many days a month you dedicate towards welfare of the society like cleaning neighbourhood?	1.000	.532
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

- Varimax rotation was applied to aid interpretability and prevent undue isolated loading. This indicates that the items loading in one factor are independent from that of the other factors. The loadings on each of the 14 factors were analyzed from the Rotated Factor matrix.
- Among the 14 factors, single and cross factor loadings were observed. In exploratory factor analysis (CFA), it is common to constrain cross-loadings to zero values, assuming therefore that each item loads only on a single construct. However, items are rarely related to a single construct, so this practice is been in practice. Table no 130. (<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.923877/full>).

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Table no.130: Rotated Component Matrix

Rotated Component Matrix ^a														
	Component													
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
26. Do you find your enthusiasm reducing as the day progresses?	.689													

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

6. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?	.662													
24. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?	.630													

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>8. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)</p>	<p>. 5 5 3</p>											<p>. 3 1 9</p>		
<p>12. How often do you find yourself distracted/ confused in your daily life?</p>	<p>. 5 4 8</p>													

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>36. Are you emotionally sensitive like sad/anxious/irritable/angry towards tough situations</p>	<p>.493</p>										<p>.408</p>			
<p>35. How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?</p>	<p>.463</p>													
<p>41. Do you procrastinate on your work?</p>	<p>.452</p>				<p>.326</p>			<p>.317</p>						

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

5. How often do you perform your daily activities (professional/personal) with complete interest?	. 4 4 9													
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OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>16. How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?</p>	<p>. 3 9 6</p>	<p>. 3 4 8</p>												
<p>1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?</p>		<p>. 6 9 8</p>												

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>13. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?</p>	<p>. 3 0 7</p>	<p>. 6 2 4</p>												
<p>39. Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?</p>		<p>. 6 1 6</p>												

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>14. Have you ever faced problems due of your absent-minded/negligent behavior?</p>	<p>. 3 8 4</p>	<p>. 6 0 9</p>												
<p>19. On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?</p>		<p>. 4 0 2</p>	<p>. 3 4 3</p>											

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>34. What do you do when you observe barriers that block the way to your success?</p>			<p>. 6 8 5</p>											
<p>33. Do you bounce back after a failure?</p>			<p>. 6 0 0</p>											
<p>28. How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?</p>			<p>. 5 6 6</p>											

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>21. Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?</p>			<p style="text-align: center;">.485</p>											
<p>29. Do you think your educational qualification/development of skills has added to your work efficiency?</p>			<p style="text-align: center;">.477</p>											

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

40. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?			.389											
10. Do you feel that it is the parents/s pouse's responsibility to take care of the family?				.702										
11. Does your family ever remind you to appreciate for the favors received ?				.611										

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>43. Do you consider your parents'/ spouse's/ children's suggestions over your own during major decisions?</p>					<p style="text-align: center;">.666</p>									
<p>18. Do you skip daily routines like washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?</p>				<p style="text-align: center;">.317</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">.509</p>									

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

31. Do you believe in living a peaceful life without taking risks?			.333			.617								
44. Regardless of who is at fault, do you apologize to your parents/souse/children?						.527								
20. Have you been blamed for talking rudely by your family?						.695								

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

2.How often do you recheck to ensure the work is done?							.487			.420				
9. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/s pouse/fri ends/nei ghbours ?							.409							

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>23. Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family/friends/colleagues?</p>								<p style="text-align: center;">.613</p>						
<p>22. How often do you express your emotions inappropriately?</p>								<p style="text-align: center;">.607</p>						

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

7. Is it common for you to only be interested in things you are familiar with? For eg: doctors who are willing to write movie reviews but unwilling to learn computer coding.	.	3	6	5						.	4	8	8						
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OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

3. How often do you need help remembering important dates, events, and names of people?										.690				
4. How often do you need tricks and techniques for memory? For eg: mnemonics, sing it out, etc.										.512				
37. Do you find it easy to recover emotionally after a crisis?											.764			

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>15. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?</p>	<p>. 3 3 0</p>	<p>. 3 2 2</p>									<p>- . 3 7 1</p>			
<p>27. How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?</p>	<p>. 3 3 0</p>											<p>. 6 5 8</p>		
<p>25. Did you ever quit/change jobs because it got boring?</p>												<p>. 5 3 6</p>		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

45. How many days a month you dedicate towards welfare of the society like cleaning neighbourhood?															.694
38. Are you concerned about the future consequence while working ?															.769
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.															
a. Rotation converged in 47 iterations.															

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

STEP 4- Scale Evaluation: Test of Reliability and Validity**Reliability tests – Internal Consistency by Cronbach’s Alpha**

Reliability Statistics - Table #131

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.868	45

External – by Test -Retest Reliability Table #132

Correlations			
		Test_Total_Sattva	Retest_Total_Sattva
Test_Total_Sattva	Pearson Correlation	1	.970**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	300	300
Retest_Total_Sattva	Pearson Correlation	.970**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

0.9 shows a positive correlation between the variables.

Table #133 - Item Analysis

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?	96.57	121.196	.303	.866
2. How often do you recheck to ensure the work is done?	96.73	122.746	.137	.869
3. How often do you need help remembering important dates, events, and names of people?	96.64	120.859	.276	.867

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

4. How often do you need tricks and techniques for memory? For eg: mnemonics, sing it out, etc.	96.68	121.936	.274	.866
5. How often do you perform your daily activities (professional/personal) with complete interest?	96.46	119.433	.446	.864
6. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?	96.76	115.967	.546	.861
7. Is it common for you to only be interested in things you are familiar with? For eg: doctors who are willing to write movie reviews but unwilling to learn computer coding.	96.94	120.789	.297	.866
8. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)	96.66	118.632	.411	.864
9. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse/friends/neighbours?	96.48	119.160	.390	.864
10. Do you feel that it is the parents/spouse's responsibility to take care of the family?	96.15	122.257	.214	.867
11. Does your family ever remind you to appreciate for the favors received?	96.37	121.256	.263	.867
12. How often do you find yourself distracted/ confused in your daily life?	97.06	119.993	.439	.864
13. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?	96.58	117.355	.529	.862
14. Have you ever faced problems due of your absent-minded/negligent behavior?	96.70	117.938	.515	.862

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

15. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?	96.68	119.383	.412	.864
16. How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?	96.54	118.878	.405	.864
17. Do you wear the same clothes for two straight days?	96.55	121.158	.218	.868
18. Do you skip daily routines like washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?	96.17	120.913	.350	.865
19. On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?	96.64	119.521	.355	.865
20. Have you been blamed for talking rudely by your family?	96.57	120.346	.279	.867
21. Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?	96.45	119.473	.423	.864
22. How often do you express your emotions inappropriately?	96.77	120.526	.375	.865
23. Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family/friends/colleagues?	96.73	119.136	.345	.865
24. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?	96.79	117.861	.510	.862
25. Did you ever quit/change jobs because it got boring?	96.42	120.967	.291	.866
26. Do you find your enthusiasm reducing as the day progresses?	96.84	118.249	.527	.862
27. How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?	96.75	120.691	.312	.866

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

28. How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?	96.52	120.244	.368	.865
29. Do you think your educational qualification/ development of skills has added to your work efficiency?	96.36	120.277	.329	.866
30. Have you not received appreciation/awards/rewards for your skills in managing your duties?	96.80	123.643	.118	.869
31. Do you believe in living a peaceful life without taking risks?	96.62	121.742	.205	.868
32. Do you invest your hard-earned money and time in a new venture?	96.77	122.855	.165	.868
33. Do you bounce back after a failure?	96.46	118.824	.417	.864
34. What do you do when you observe barriers that block the way to your success?	96.47	118.571	.471	.863
35. How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?	96.89	119.479	.403	.864
36. Are you emotionally sensitive like sad/anxious/irritable/angry towards tough situations	97.05	119.814	.376	.865
37. Do you find it easy to recover emotionally after a crisis?	96.71	122.026	.266	.867
38. Are you concerned about the future consequence while working?	96.58	125.756	-.046	.872
39. Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?	96.60	118.447	.454	.863
40. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?	96.49	119.395	.392	.864
41. Do you procrastinate on your work?	96.91	119.016	.442	.864

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

42. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?	96.65	119.252	.394	.864
43. Do you consider your parents'/spouse's/children's suggestions over your own during major decisions?	96.64	122.498	.181	.868
44. Regardless of who is at fault, do you apologize to your parents/spouse/children?	96.34	122.648	.147	.869
45. How many days a month you dedicate towards welfare of the society like cleaning neighbourhood?	97.71	124.148	.095	.869

- Based on item analysis, corrected item total correlation , any question with <0.3 value were deleted and hence a final of 28 Questions were retained.
- Question NO.
1,5,6,8,9,12,13,14,15,16,18,19,21,22,23,24,26,27,28,29,33,34,35,36,39,40,41,42 were included to the final questionnaire as they had item total correlation score more than 0.3 indicating they represent the construct after applying on 300 respondents.
- Domain Kalyanabhinivesha was deleted due to poor score on item total correlation thus indicating poor comprehension among the respondents.

Phase 3**Scale Standardisation****Confirmatory Factor Analysis**

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is a statistical technique used to validate the factor structure that was previously identified through Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) or theoretical reasoning. CFA is part of structural equation modeling (SEM) and requires the researcher to specify in advance the number of factors and the relationships among observed variables and underlying latent constructs.

Purpose of CFA

The main objectives of CFA include:

- **Validation of the Factor Structure:** CFA tests whether the data fits a hypothesized measurement model based on established theoretical frameworks.
- **Testing Specific Hypotheses:** Researchers can test specific hypotheses about the relationships among observed variables and latent factors.

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis N
1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?	2.09	.690	493
2. How often do you engage in activities other than your academic or professional interests?	1.93	.736	493
3. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?	2.04	.738	493

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

4. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)	2.02	.783	493
5. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse?	2.23	.724	493
6. How often do you find yourself distracted/ confused in your daily life?	1.93	.635	493
7. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?	2.16	.719	493
8. Have you anytime faced problems because of your absent-minded/negligent behavior?	2.10	.703	493
9. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?	1.95	.725	493
10. How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?	2.16	.754	493
11. Can you skip daily routines like, washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?	2.32	.787	493
12. On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?	2.05	.769	493
13. Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?	2.12	.775	493
14. How often have you cried, shouted, or taken your anger out of place?	1.99	.772	493
15. Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family?	1.97	.788	493

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

16. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?	2.02	.714	493
17. Do you find your enthusiasm reduces as the day progresses?	1.95	.742	493
18. How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?	1.95	.695	493
19. How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?	2.14	.667	493
20. Do you think your educational qualification/ development of skills has added to your work efficiency?	2.20	.778	493
21. Do you bounce back after a failure?	2.20	.687	493
22. Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success?	2.12	.712	493
23. How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?	1.88	.691	493
24. Do you consider yourself an emotionally sensitive person in tough situations?	1.85	.710	493
25. Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?	2.05	.735	493
26. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?	2.22	.703	493
27. Do you procrastinate on your work?	2.07	.724	493
28. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?	2.11	.780	493

communalities" refer to the amount of variance in each variable that is shared or common with other variables in the dataset. Essentially, it represents how much of the variance of each variable can be explained by the underlying factors extracted in the analysis.

As a rule of thumb, you generally want communalities to be above **0.4 or 0.5** after extraction, as this suggests that the factors account for a sufficient portion of the variance in the variables. If communalities are consistently low, it might be worth reconsidering the inclusion of certain variables or the factor model itself.

In factor analysis, communalities typically range from 0 to 1, and the acceptable value depends on the context and goal of the analysis. Here are some general guidelines:

1. **Low communalities (< 0.3):** These indicate that a variable does not share much variance with other variables. If most variables have low communalities, it may suggest that factor analysis is not suitable for the data.
2. **Moderate communalities (0.3 to 0.7):** These are considered acceptable in many analyses, suggesting that a reasonable amount of variance is shared between variables and the underlying factors. Table 135
3. **High communalities (> 0.7):** These are ideal because they indicate that the variables are highly associated with the common factors, explaining a large proportion of their variance.

Table 135 - Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?	1.000	.568
2. How often do you engage in activities other than your academic or professional interests?	1.000	.774
3. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?	1.000	.752
4. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)	1.000	.678
5. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse?	1.000	.843
6. How often do you find yourself distracted/confused in your daily life?	1.000	.714
7. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?	1.000	.741
8. Have you anytime faced problems because of your absent-minded/ negligent behavior?	1.000	.630
9. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?	1.000	.632
10. How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?	1.000	.668
11. Can you skip daily routines like, washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?	1.000	.744
12. On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?	1.000	.756
13. Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?	1.000	.780
14. How often have you cried, shouted, or taken your anger out of place?	1.000	.753
15. Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family?	1.000	.647

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

16. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?	1.000	.805
17. Do you find your enthusiasm reduces as the day progresses?	1.000	.691
18. How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?	1.000	.723
19. How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?	1.000	.690
20. Do you think your educational qualification/development of skills has added to your work efficiency?	1.000	.710
21. Do you bounce back after a failure?	1.000	.825
22. Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success?	1.000	.741
23. How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?	1.000	.601
24. Do you consider yourself an emotionally sensitive person in tough situations?	1.000	.713
25. Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?	1.000	.713
26. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?	1.000	.740
27. Do you procrastinate on your work?	1.000	.576
28. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?	1.000	.681

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 136 - Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
	1	9.950	35.536	35.536	9.950	35.536	35.536	3.809	13.604
2	2.014	7.193	42.729	2.014	7.193	42.729	2.929	10.462	24.066
3	1.297	4.631	47.360	1.297	4.631	47.360	2.160	7.714	31.780
4	1.183	4.225	51.585	1.183	4.225	51.585	2.008	7.172	38.952
5	1.110	3.966	55.551	1.110	3.966	55.551	2.005	7.161	46.113
6	1.020	3.643	59.194	1.020	3.643	59.194	1.593	5.689	51.802
7	.925	3.305	62.499	.925	3.305	62.499	1.531	5.469	57.271
8	.840	3.000	65.498	.840	3.000	65.498	1.341	4.790	62.060
9	.783	2.796	68.294	.783	2.796	68.294	1.272	4.541	66.602
10	.763	2.725	71.019	.763	2.725	71.019	1.237	4.418	71.019
11	.720	2.571	73.590						
12	.660	2.358	75.948						
13	.630	2.251	78.200						
14	.616	2.202	80.401						
15	.579	2.068	82.470						
16	.537	1.917	84.387						
17	.507	1.812	86.199						
18	.490	1.751	87.950						
19	.441	1.576	89.526						
20	.418	1.493	91.020						
21	.409	1.461	92.481						
22	.370	1.322	93.803						

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

23	.363	1.295	95.098						
24	.338	1.207	96.305						
25	.315	1.125	97.430						
26	.263	.940	98.370						
27	.239	.854	99.224						
28	.217	.776	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

- The analysis of the scree plot showed that there were 10 factors with eigenvalue above 1. Therefore, the remaining principal components account for a very small proportion of the variability (close to zero) and are probably unimportant.
- Scree because the plot looks like stones collected at the foot of a mountain after rolling off from the top. Eigenvalue is a measure of variance.

Figure no.2

The **Rotated Component Matrix** in SPSS is an output from **factor analysis** or **principal component analysis (PCA)** that shows the correlations between the variables and the factors after rotation. The goal of rotation is to make the output easier to interpret by simplifying the factor structure.

Varimax was used Table 137

Scores higher the better. Less than 1 shows weak associations

	Component									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?										
2. How often do you engage in activities other than your academic or professional interests?									.778	
3. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?				.744						
4. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)						.607				
5. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse?								.867		
6. How often do you find yourself distracted/ confused in your daily life?	.718									
7. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?	.693									

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

8. Have you anytime faced problems because of your absent-minded/negligent behavior?	.576									
9. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?	.535									
10. How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?	.745									
11. Can you skip daily routines like, washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?										
12. On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?		.761								
13. Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?		.725								
14. How often have you cried, shouted, or taken your anger out of place?			.721							

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

15. Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family?			.590						
16. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?			.738						
17. Do you find your enthusiasm reduces as the day progresses?	.583								
18. How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?					.666				
19. How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?				.569					
20. Do you think your educational qualification/ development of skills has added to your work efficiency?				.777					
21. Do you bounce back after a failure?						.824			
22. Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success?						.631			
23. How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?									

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

24. Do you consider yourself an emotionally sensitive person in tough situations?			.723							
25. Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?			.510							
26. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?										.711
27. Do you procrastinate on your work?										
28. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?			.632							
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.										
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.										
a. Rotation converged in 25 iterations.										

Distribution of components in rotated space as compiled below

Component Plot in Rotated Space

Figure 3 -Component Plot in Rotated Space

Scale Refinement into 10 factors likewise 10 domains used for standardization

Statistical Analysis for Standardisation

- Norm development in scale standardization is a systematic process that establishes benchmarks or reference points (norms) which can be used to interpret scores obtained from a particular scale. Establishing norms helps researchers, practitioners, and decision-makers understand where individual scores fall relative to a defined population, essentially translating raw score results into meaningful interpretations.
- Norm is established on 2 sample sets of 250 healthy volunteers and 250 patients of common mental disorders. Common guidelines suggest a minimum of 100-300 respondents, although larger samples are often preferred for more stable estimates of norms.

Descriptive statistics for Normality

For 500 Respondents (250 Healthy volunteers and 250 patients of CMD)

Table #138 -Descriptives				
			Statistic	Std. Error
1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?	Mean		2.08	.031
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.02	
		Upper Bound	2.14	
	5% Trimmed Mean		2.09	
	Median		2.00	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Variance	.474	
	Std. Deviation	.688	
	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	1	
	Skewness	-.110	.109
	Kurtosis	-.887	.218
2. How often do you	Mean	1.93	.033
engage in	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.86
activities other		Upper Bound	1.99
than your	5% Trimmed Mean	1.92	
academic or	Median	2.00	
professional	Variance	.542	
interests?	Std. Deviation	.736	
	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	1	
	Skewness	.117	.109
	Kurtosis	-1.145	.218
3. Do you find it	Mean	2.03	.033

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.97	
		Upper Bound	2.10	
	5% Trimmed Mean		2.04	
	Median		2.00	
	Variance		.546	
	Std. Deviation		.739	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		2	
	Skewness		-.054	.109
	Kurtosis		-1.163	.218
	4. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)	Mean		2.01
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	1.95	
		Upper Bound	2.08	
5% Trimmed Mean		2.02		
Median		2.00		
Variance		.615		
Std. Deviation		.784		
Minimum		1		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	2	
	Skewness	-.025	.109
	Kurtosis	-1.372	.218
5. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse?	Mean	2.22	.032
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.16
		Upper Bound	2.29
	5% Trimmed Mean	2.25	
	Median	2.00	
	Variance	.527	
	Std. Deviation	.726	
	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	1	
	Skewness	-.370	.109
	Kurtosis	-1.041	.218
	6. How often do you find yourself distracted/	Mean	1.93
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	1.87

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

confused in your daily life?		Upper Bound	1.98	
	5% Trimmed Mean		1.92	
	Median		2.00	
	Variance		.405	
	Std. Deviation		.637	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		0	
	Skewness		.063	.109
	Kurtosis		-.540	.218
7. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?	Mean		2.15	.032
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.09	
		Upper Bound	2.22	
	5% Trimmed Mean		2.17	
	Median		2.00	
	Variance		.518	
	Std. Deviation		.720	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Interquartile Range	1	
	Skewness	-.235	.109
	Kurtosis	-1.049	.218
8. Have you anytime faced problems because of your absent-minded/negligent behavior?	Mean	2.09	.032
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.03
		Upper Bound	2.16
	5% Trimmed Mean	2.10	
	Median	2.00	
	Variance	.498	
	Std. Deviation	.706	
	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	1	
	Skewness	-.135	.109
	Kurtosis	-.986	.218
	9. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?	Mean	1.95
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	1.88
		Upper Bound	2.01
5% Trimmed Mean		1.94	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Median	2.00		
	Variance	.524		
	Std. Deviation	.724		
	Minimum	1		
	Maximum	3		
	Range	2		
	Interquartile Range	1		
	Skewness	.082	.109	
	Kurtosis	-1.086	.218	
10. How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?	Mean	2.16	.034	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.10	
		Upper Bound	2.23	
	5% Trimmed Mean	2.18		
	Median	2.00		
	Variance	.570		
	Std. Deviation	.755		
	Minimum	1		
	Maximum	3		
	Range	2		
	Interquartile Range	1		
	Skewness	-.281	.109	
	Kurtosis	-1.202	.218	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

11. Can you skip daily routines like, washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?	Mean	2.31	.035	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.24	
		Upper Bound	2.38	
	5% Trimmed Mean	2.34		
	Median	3.00		
	Variance	.623		
	Std. Deviation	.789		
	Minimum	1		
	Maximum	3		
	Range	2		
	Interquartile Range	1		
	Skewness	-.610	.109	
	Kurtosis	-1.138	.218	
12. On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?	Mean	2.04	.034	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.97	
		Upper Bound	2.11	
	5% Trimmed Mean	2.04		
	Median	2.00		
	Variance	.594		
	Std. Deviation	.771		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	2	
	Skewness	-.065	.109
	Kurtosis	-1.311	.218
13. Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?	Mean	2.11	.035
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.04
		Upper Bound	2.18
	5% Trimmed Mean	2.12	
	Median	2.00	
	Variance	.606	
	Std. Deviation	.778	
	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	2	
	Skewness	-.190	.109
	Kurtosis	-1.325	.218
14. How often have you cried, shouted, or taken your	Mean	1.99	.035
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.93

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

anger out of place?		Upper Bound	2.06	
	5% Trimmed Mean		1.99	
	Median		2.00	
	Variance		.599	
	Std. Deviation		.774	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		2	
	Skewness		.010	.109
	Kurtosis		-1.329	.218
15. Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family?	Mean		1.97	.035
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.90	
		Upper Bound	2.04	
	5% Trimmed Mean		1.97	
	Median		2.00	
	Variance		.620	
	Std. Deviation		.788	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
Range		2		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Interquartile Range	2	
	Skewness	.049	.109
	Kurtosis	-1.385	.218
16. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?	Mean	2.02	.032
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.95
		Upper Bound	2.08
	5% Trimmed Mean	2.02	
	Median	2.00	
	Variance	.513	
	Std. Deviation	.716	
	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	1	
	Skewness	-.023	.109
	Kurtosis	-1.044	.218
	17. Do you find your enthusiasm reduces as the day progresses?	Mean	1.94
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	1.88
		Upper Bound	2.01
5% Trimmed Mean		1.94	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Median	2.00	
	Variance	.554	
	Std. Deviation	.744	
	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	2	
	Skewness	.090	.109
	Kurtosis	-1.188	.218
18. How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?	Mean	1.95	.031
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.89
		Upper Bound	2.01
	5% Trimmed Mean	1.95	
	Median	2.00	
	Variance	.483	
	Std. Deviation	.695	
	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	1	
	Skewness	.064	.109
Kurtosis	-.922	.218	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

19. How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?	Mean		2.14	.030
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.08	
		Upper Bound	2.19	
	5% Trimmed Mean		2.15	
	Median		2.00	
	Variance		.446	
	Std. Deviation		.668	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-.163	.109
	Kurtosis		-.776	.218
	20. Do you think your educational qualification/development of skills has added to your work efficiency?	Mean		2.19
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	2.12	
		Upper Bound	2.26	
5% Trimmed Mean		2.21		
Median		2.00		
Variance		.607		
Std. Deviation		.779		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Minimum	1		
	Maximum	3		
	Range	2		
	Interquartile Range	1		
	Skewness	-.345	.109	
	Kurtosis	-1.277	.218	
21. Do you bounce back after a failure?	Mean	2.20	.031	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.14	
		Upper Bound	2.26	
	5% Trimmed Mean	2.22		
	Median	2.00		
	Variance	.474		
	Std. Deviation	.689		
	Minimum	1		
	Maximum	3		
	Range	2		
	Interquartile Range	1		
	Skewness	-.287	.109	
	Kurtosis	-.891	.218	
	22. Do you observe barriers can block the way to your	Mean	2.11	.032
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	2.05	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

success?		Upper Bound	2.17	
	5% Trimmed Mean		2.12	
	Median		2.00	
	Variance		.507	
	Std. Deviation		.712	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-.162	.109
	Kurtosis		-1.018	.218
23.How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?	Mean		1.88	.031
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.82	
		Upper Bound	1.94	
	5% Trimmed Mean		1.87	
	Median		2.00	
	Variance		.473	
	Std. Deviation		.688	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Interquartile Range	1	
	Skewness	.157	.109
	Kurtosis	-.886	.218
24. Do you consider yourself an emotionally sensitive person in tough situations?	Mean	1.84	.032
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.78
		Upper Bound	1.91
	5% Trimmed Mean	1.83	
	Median	2.00	
	Variance	.505	
	Std. Deviation	.710	
	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	1	
	Skewness	.234	.109
	Kurtosis	-1.003	.218
	25. Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?	Mean	2.05
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	1.98
		Upper Bound	2.11
5% Trimmed Mean		2.05	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Median	2.00		
	Variance	.541		
	Std. Deviation	.736		
	Minimum	1		
	Maximum	3		
	Range	2		
	Interquartile Range	1		
	Skewness	-.072	.109	
	Kurtosis	-1.145	.218	
26. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?	Mean	2.22	.032	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.16	
		Upper Bound	2.28	
	5% Trimmed Mean	2.24		
	Median	2.00		
	Variance	.497		
	Std. Deviation	.705		
	Minimum	1		
	Maximum	3		
	Range	2		
	Interquartile Range	1		
	Skewness	-.338	.109	
	Kurtosis	-.956	.218	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

27. Do you procrastinate on your work?	Mean		2.06	.032
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.00	
		Upper Bound	2.13	
	5% Trimmed Mean		2.07	
	Median		2.00	
	Variance		.527	
	Std. Deviation		.726	
	Minimum		1	
	Maximum		3	
	Range		2	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-.095	.109
	Kurtosis		-1.096	.218
28. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?	Mean		2.10	.035
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.03	
		Upper Bound	2.16	
	5% Trimmed Mean		2.11	
	Median		2.00	
	Variance		.612	
	Std. Deviation		.782	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Minimum	1	
	Maximum	3	
	Range	2	
	Interquartile Range	2	
	Skewness	-.170	.109
	Kurtosis	-1.347	.218

Measures of Central Tendency for each question suggestive of Normal Distribution as shown in the Table.

Z Score Calculation – Table no 140

- **Z-Score: Represents how many standard deviations a data point is away from the mean. A Z-score of 0 corresponds to the mean of the distribution.**

Z score for each Raw score

Sl No	Raw score	Corresponding Z score
1.	43	-1.20999
2.	69	.93217
3.	60	.19065
4.	62	.35543
5.	57	-.05652
6.	62	.35543
7.	64	.52021
8.	42	-1.29238
9.	30	-2.28107
10.	48	-.79804
11.	62	.35543

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

12.	40	-1.45716
13.	52	-.46847
14.	42	-1.29238
15.	58	.02587
16.	65	.60261
17.	68	.84978
18.	45	-1.04521
19.	54	-.30369
20.	47	-.88043
21.	61	.27304
22.	48	-.79804
23.	61	.27304
24.	72	1.17934
25.	33	-2.03390
26.	67	.76739
27.	43	-1.20999
28.	55	-.22130
29.	65	.60261
30.	52	-.46847
31.	63	.43782
32.	44	-1.12760
33.	43	-1.20999
34.	52	-.46847
35.	67	.76739
36.	45	-1.04521

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

37.	49	-.71565
38.	62	.35543
39.	60	.19065
40.	63	.43782
41.	44	-1.12760
42.	69	.93217
43.	61	.27304
44.	51	-.55086
45.	66	.68500
46.	34	-1.95150
47.	57	-.05652
48.	60	.19065
49.	56	-.13891
50.	63	.43782
51.	43	-1.20999
52.	73	1.26173
53.	46	-.96282
54.	41	-1.37477
55.	71	1.09695
56.	51	-.55086
57.	51	-.55086
58.	29	-2.36346
59.	71	1.09695
60.	77	1.59129
61.	49	-.71565

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

62.	75	1.42651
63.	53	-.38608
64.	66	.68500
65.	62	.35543
66.	51	-.55086
67.	71	1.09695
68.	73	1.26173
69.	62	.35543
70.	72	1.17934
71.	54	-.30369
72.	55	-.22130
73.	49	-.71565
74.	44	-1.12760
75.	73	1.26173
76.	65	.60261
77.	57	-.05652
78.	70	1.01456
79.	55	-.22130
80.	72	1.17934
81.	58	.02587
82.	76	1.50890
83.	63	.43782
84.	68	.84978
85.	60	.19065
86.	67	.76739

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

87.	68	.84978
88.	71	1.09695
89.	63	.43782
90.	69	.93217
91.	42	-1.29238
92.	68	.84978
93.	56	-.13891
94.	64	.52021
95.	49	-.71565
96.	83	2.08564
97.	56	-.13891
98.	72	1.17934
99.	64	.52021
100.	28	-2.44585
101.	56	-.13891
102.	34	-1.95150
103.	63	.43782
104.	63	.43782
105.	55	-.22130
106.	45	-1.04521
107.	68	.84978
108.	57	-.05652
109.	81	1.92086
110.	82	2.00325
111.	81	1.92086

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

112.	62	.35543
113.	43	-1.20999
114.	82	2.00325
115.	78	1.67368
116.	81	1.92086
117.	78	1.67368
118.	73	1.26173
119.	53	-.38608
120.	43	-1.20999
121.	40	-1.45716
122.	53	-.38608
123.	60	.19065
124.	65	.60261
125.	75	1.42651
126.	83	2.08564
127.	52	-.46847
128.	71	1.09695
129.	79	1.75607
130.	74	1.34412
131.	64	.52021
132.	55	-.22130
133.	47	-.88043
134.	50	-.63325
135.	41	-1.37477
136.	51	-.55086

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

137.	39	-1.53955
138.	67	.76739
139.	61	.27304
140.	39	-1.53955
141.	58	.02587
142.	55	-.22130
143.	57	-.05652
144.	69	.93217
145.	65	.60261
146.	52	-.46847
147.	63	.43782
148.	40	-1.45716
149.	59	.10826
150.	59	.10826
151.	49	-.71565
152.	53	-.38608
153.	72	1.17934
154.	76	1.50890
155.	54	-.30369
156.	64	.52021
157.	60	.19065
158.	66	.68500
159.	64	.52021
160.	69	.93217
161.	83	2.08564

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

162.	84	2.16803
163.	70	1.01456
164.	57	-.05652
165.	81	1.92086
166.	73	1.26173
167.	68	.84978
168.	80	1.83847
169.	48	-.79804
170.	57	-.05652
171.	84	2.16803
172.	51	-.55086
173.	68	.84978
174.	63	.43782
175.	38	-1.62194
176.	42	-1.29238
177.	44	-1.12760
178.	43	-1.20999
179.	64	.52021
180.	57	-.05652
181.	51	-.55086
182.	66	.68500
183.	77	1.59129
184.	84	2.16803
185.	33	-2.03390
186.	37	-1.70433

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

187.	44	-1.12760
188.	31	-2.19868
189.	53	-.38608
190.	45	-1.04521
191.	39	-1.53955
192.	30	-2.28107
193.	52	-.46847
194.	54	-.30369
195.	81	1.92086
196.	66	.68500
197.	57	-.05652
198.	39	-1.53955
199.	50	-.63325
200.	61	.27304
201.	62	.35543
202.	58	.02587
203.	47	-.88043
204.	72	1.17934
205.	49	-.71565
206.	71	1.09695
207.	47	-.88043
208.	40	-1.45716
209.	37	-1.70433
210.	45	-1.04521
211.	76	1.50890

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

212.	43	-1.20999
213.	35	-1.86911
214.	45	-1.04521
215.	73	1.26173
216.	40	-1.45716
217.	43	-1.20999
218.	69	.93217
219.	64	.52021
220.	64	.52021
221.	64	.52021
222.	40	-1.45716
223.	52	-.46847
224.	40	-1.45716
225.	52	-.46847
226.	40	-1.45716
227.	52	-.46847
228.	40	-1.45716
229.	52	-.46847
230.	81	1.92086
231.	82	2.00325
232.	81	1.92086
233.	62	.35543
234.	43	-1.20999
235.	82	2.00325
236.	78	1.67368

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

237.	81	1.92086
238.	78	1.67368
239.	73	1.26173
240.	60	.19065
241.	62	.35543
242.	57	-.05652
243.	62	.35543
244.	60	.19065
245.	62	.35543
246.	57	-.05652
247.	62	.35543
248.	60	.19065
249.	62	.35543
250.	57	-.05652
251.	62	.35543
252.	60	.19065
253.	62	.35543
254.	57	-.05652
255.	62	.35543
256.	33	-2.03390
257.	55	-.22130
258.	71	1.09695
259.	77	1.59129
260.	49	-.71565
261.	75	1.42651

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

262.	51	-.55086
263.	55	-.22130
264.	52	-.46847
265.	52	-.46847
266.	63	.43782
267.	40	-1.45716
268.	52	-.46847
269.	40	-1.45716
270.	52	-.46847
271.	57	-.05652
272.	40	-1.45716
273.	52	-.46847
274.	40	-1.45716
275.	52	-.46847
276.	67	.76739
277.	73	1.26173
278.	68	.84978
279.	51	-.55086
280.	73	1.26173
281.	58	.02587
282.	64	.52021
283.	61	.27304
284.	66	.68500
285.	57	-.05652
286.	50	-.63325

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

287.	58	.02587
288.	70	1.01456
289.	69	.93217
290.	73	1.26173
291.	67	.76739
292.	60	.19065
293.	55	-.22130
294.	56	-.13891
295.	63	.43782
296.	56	-.13891
297.	56	-.13891
298.	69	.93217
299.	67	.76739
300.	62	.35543
301.	68	.84978
302.	59	.10826
303.	63	.43782
304.	55	-.22130
305.	56	-.13891
306.	52	-.46847
307.	70	1.01456
308.	70	1.01456
309.	56	-.13891
310.	53	-.38608
311.	61	.27304

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

312.	77	1.59129
313.	75	1.42651
314.	69	.93217
315.	63	.43782
316.	65	.60261
317.	47	-.88043
318.	67	.76739
319.	72	1.17934
320.	72	1.17934
321.	52	-.46847
322.	63	.43782
323.	66	.68500
324.	58	.02587
325.	68	.84978
326.	62	.35543
327.	63	.43782
328.	64	.52021
329.	59	.10826
330.	63	.43782
331.	70	1.01456
332.	67	.76739
333.	55	-.22130
334.	57	-.05652
335.	70	1.01456
336.	58	.02587

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

337.	66	.68500
338.	54	-.30369
339.	61	.27304
340.	54	-.30369
341.	49	-.71565
342.	54	-.30369
343.	64	.52021
344.	66	.68500
345.	53	-.38608
346.	73	1.26173
347.	65	.60261
348.	66	.68500
349.	55	-.22130
350.	72	1.17934
351.	70	1.01456
352.	67	.76739
353.	57	-.05652
354.	47	-.88043
355.	54	-.30369
356.	78	1.67368
357.	56	-.13891
358.	64	.52021
359.	69	.93217
360.	75	1.42651
361.	65	.60261

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

362.	62	.35543
363.	68	.84978
364.	64	.52021
365.	59	.10826
366.	66	.68500
367.	80	1.83847
368.	70	1.01456
369.	68	.84978
370.	61	.27304
371.	61	.27304
372.	75	1.42651
373.	66	.68500
374.	77	1.59129
375.	74	1.34412
376.	58	.02587
377.	54	-.30369
378.	56	-.13891
379.	68	.84978
380.	68	.84978
381.	46	-.96282
382.	66	.68500
383.	64	.52021
384.	55	-.22130
385.	66	.68500
386.	60	.19065

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

387.	54	-.30369
388.	49	-.71565
389.	58	.02587
390.	53	-.38608
391.	69	.93217
392.	54	-.30369
393.	61	.27304
394.	68	.84978
395.	71	1.09695
396.	79	1.75607
397.	51	-.55086
398.	55	-.22130
399.	68	.84978
400.	44	-1.12760
401.	54	-.30369
402.	40	-1.45716
403.	66	.68500
404.	55	-.22130
405.	47	-.88043
406.	53	-.38608
407.	63	.43782
408.	55	-.22130
409.	67	.76739
410.	61	.27304
411.	48	-.79804

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

412.	44	-1.12760
413.	53	-.38608
414.	42	-1.29238
415.	49	-.71565
416.	42	-1.29238
417.	30	-2.28107
418.	44	-1.12760
419.	30	-2.28107
420.	53	-.38608
421.	39	-1.53955
422.	42	-1.29238
423.	40	-1.45716
424.	52	-.46847
425.	39	-1.53955
426.	44	-1.12760
427.	40	-1.45716
428.	53	-.38608
429.	30	-2.28107
430.	52	-.46847
431.	54	-.30369
432.	44	-1.12760
433.	50	-.63325
434.	44	-1.12760
435.	31	-2.19868
436.	52	-.46847

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

437.	54	-.30369
438.	30	-2.28107
439.	52	-.46847
440.	54	-.30369
441.	49	-.71565
442.	52	-.46847
443.	63	.43782
444.	44	-1.12760
445.	43	-1.20999
446.	52	-.46847
447.	67	.76739
448.	45	-1.04521
449.	49	-.71565
450.	62	.35543
451.	60	.19065
452.	63	.43782
453.	44	-1.12760
454.	69	.93217
455.	61	.27304
456.	51	-.55086
457.	66	.68500
458.	52	-.46847
459.	63	.43782
460.	44	-1.12760
461.	43	-1.20999

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

462.	52	-.46847
463.	67	.76739
464.	45	-1.04521
465.	49	-.71565
466.	62	.35543
467.	60	.19065
468.	63	.43782
469.	44	-1.12760
470.	69	.93217
471.	61	.27304
472.	51	-.55086
473.	66	.68500
474.	28	-2.44585
475.	28	-2.44585
476.	50	-.63325
477.	60	.19065
478.	38	-1.62194
479.	44	-1.12760
480.	66	.68500
481.	55	-.22130
482.	59	.10826
483.	57	-.05652
484.	51	-.55086
485.	53	-.38608
486.	61	.27304

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

487.	39	-1.53955
488.	51	-.55086
489.	39	-1.53955
490.	40	-1.45716
491.	51	-.55086
492.	40	-1.45716
493.	47	-.88043
494.	61	.27304
495.	48	-.79804
496.	64	.52021
497.	42	-1.29238
498.	30	-2.28107
499.	48	-.79804
500.	62	.35543

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

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- **Percentile:** Indicates the percentage of scores in a distribution that fall below the corresponding Z-score.

Percentile Table 139-

Percentiles		Percentiles						
		5	10	25	50	75	90	95
Weighted Average (Definition 1)	1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	2. How often do you engage in activities other than your academic or professional interests?	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>3. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?</p>	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	<p>4. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)</p>	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>5. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse?</p>	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	<p>6. How often do you find yourself distracted/confused in your daily life?</p>	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0
	<p>7. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?</p>	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	8. Have you anytime faced problems because of your absent-minded/negligent behavior?	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	9. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>10. How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?</p>	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	<p>11. Can you skip daily routines like, washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?</p>	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>12. On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?</p>	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	<p>13. Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?</p>	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	<p>14. How often have you cried, shouted, or taken your anger out of place?</p>	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>15. Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family?</p>	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	<p>16. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?</p>	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	<p>17. Do you find your enthusiasm reduces as the day progresses?</p>	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.7	3.0	3.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	18. How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0
	19. How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	20. Do you think your educational qualification/development of skills has added to your work efficiency?	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	21. Do you bounce back after a failure?	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>22. Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success?</p>	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
	<p>23. How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?</p>	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0
	<p>24. Do you consider yourself an emotionally sensitive person in tough situations?</p>	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

25. Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
26. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
27. Do you procrastinate on your work?	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
28. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	3.0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>Tukey's Hinges</p>	<p>1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?</p>			<p>2.0</p>	<p>2.0</p>	<p>3.0</p>		
	<p>2. How often do you engage in activities other than your academic or professional interests?</p>			<p>1.0</p>	<p>2.0</p>	<p>2.0</p>		
	<p>3. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?</p>			<p>1.0</p>	<p>2.0</p>	<p>3.0</p>		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>4. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)</p>			1.0	2.0	3.0		
	<p>5. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>6. How often do you find yourself distracted/ confused in your daily life?</p>			2.0	2.0	2.0		
	<p>7. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		
	<p>8. Have you anytime faced problems because of your absent-minded/ negligent behavior?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>9. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?</p>			1.0	2.0	2.0		
	<p>10. How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>11. Can you skip daily routines like, washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?</p>			2.0	3.0	3.0		
	<p>12. On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?</p>			1.0	2.0	3.0		
	<p>13. Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?</p>			1.0	2.0	3.0		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>14. How often have you cried, shouted, or taken your anger out of place?</p>			1.0	2.0	3.0		
	<p>15. Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family?</p>			1.0	2.0	3.0		
	<p>16. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>17. Do you find your enthusiasm reduces as the day progresses?</p>			1.0	2.0	2.5		
	<p>18. How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?</p>			1.0	2.0	2.0		
	<p>19. How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>20. Do you think your educational qualification/development of skills has added to your work efficiency?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		
	<p>21. Do you bounce back after a failure?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		
	<p>22. Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		
	<p>23. How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?</p>			1.0	2.0	2.0		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	<p>24. Do you consider yourself an emotionally sensitive person in tough situations?</p>			1.0	2.0	2.0		
	<p>25. Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		
	<p>26. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		
	<p>27. Do you procrastinate on your work?</p>			2.0	2.0	3.0		

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	28. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?			1.0	2.0	3.0		
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After calculating the Z scores for all the raw scores, the range of Z-scores were divided into three levels, according to their corresponding raw scores, as shown in Table. Respondents having a score of above 56 indicate Pravara Sattva, 29- 56 indicate Madhyama Sattva and a score below 29 indicate Avara Sattva as given in table 141

Table No 141- Cut off scores

Sl No	Raw Score Range	Z Score Range	Type Of Sattva
1	Above 56	Above +1	Pravara
2	29-56	-1 to +1	Madhyama
3	Below 29	Below -1	Avara

Data Analysis in Standardisation Phase

Table #142 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * Gender Crosstabulation					
Count					
		Gender			Total
		Male	Female	Others	
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	72	177	1	250
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	18	21	1	40

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	13	18	0	31
Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	7	8	0	15
Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	7	7	0	14
Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	2	0	0	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	85	1	0	86
	Epilepsy	6	2	0	8
	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	6	11	1	18
	Unspecified symptoms	16	19	0	35
Total		233	264	3	500

Males – 233 (72 healthy and 233 Patients), Females-264(177 healthy and 87 patients) and 3 from others

Table #143 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * Age											
Crosstabulation											
Count											
		Age									Total
		18-20	21-25	26-30	31-35	36-40	41-45	46-50	51-55	56-60	
Have you been	Healthy	12	92	60	28	12	19	18	4	5	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	1	7	3	4	3	10	5	6	1	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	0	2	8	9	7	2	2	0	1	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	1	0	5	3	0	0	2	1	3	15

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	3	3	0	2	4	2	0	0	0	14
Personality Disorders	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	2	5	8	21	12	7	7	12	12	86
Epilepsy	0	3	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	3	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	4	18
Unspecified symptoms	2	2	1	0	13	15	2	0	0	35
Total	24	118	90	70	52	58	37	25	26	500

Volunteers belonging to 21-30 years attempted the most.

Table #144 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * Marital Status Crosstabulation						
Count						
		Marital Status			Total	
		Married	Unmarried	Divorced/separated		
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	97	144	9	250	
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	30	10	0	40	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	19	12	0	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	5	10	0	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	8	6	0	14
	Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	0	2	0	2
	Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	56	30	0	86
	Epilepsy	2	6	0	8
	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	14	4	0	18
	Unspecified symptoms	32	3	0	35
Total		263	228	9	500

263 married and 228 unmarried and 9 seperated respondents.

Table number 145 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * Place

Crosstabulation

Count

		Place		
		Karnataka	Out of Karnataka	Total
Have you been suffering	Healthy	134	116	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	26	14	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	23	8	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	14	1	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	9	5	14
	Personality Disorders	1	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	2
	Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	86	0	86
	Epilepsy	7	1	8
	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	11	7	18

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Unspecified symptoms	32	3	35
Total		344	156	500

344 respondents of Karnataka and 156 respondents outside Karnataka took up the study.

Table #146 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * Education Completed Crosstabulation								
Count								
		Education Completed						Total
		Uneducated	Primary	Secondary	Pre-University	Undergraduate	Postgraduate	
Have you	Healthy	4	7	8	43	107	81	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

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OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Symptoms of Anxiety (stresses, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	2	0	5	0	17	7	3
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OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	0	0	1	5	4	5	1
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OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsessions for cleanliness, repetitive behavior)	0	0	0	5	5	4	1
	Personality Disorders	0	0	0	0	1	0	1

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
Substance use (Nicotine, Alcohol, Opium etc)	14	23	25	17	7	0	8
Epilepsy	0	0	5	0	3	0	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	0	2	1	6	9	0	1
Unspecified symptoms	0	1	0	17	16	1	3

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Total	22	40	50	95	187	106	5
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Graduates and Post graduates were amongst the highest to take up the study.

Table #147 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * Employment Status Crosstabulation

Count		Employment Status		
		employed	unemployed	Total
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	124	126	250
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	12	28	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	19	12	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	4	11	15

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	5	9	14
Personality Disorders	0	1	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	81	5	86
Epilepsy	5	3	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	12	6	18
Unspecified symptoms	17	18	35
Total	280	220	500

280 (124 Healthy and 156 patients) employed, 220(126 Healthy and 94 Patients) unemployed.

Table #148 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms *

Socioeconomic Status Crosstabulation

Count		Socioeconomic Status			Total
		Lower middle class	Midle class	Upper class	
Have you been	Healthy	13	216	21	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	3	36	1	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	1	27	3	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	0	10	5	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	2	10	2	14
	Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	0	1	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	12	64	10	86
	Epilepsy	0	3	5	8
	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	0	17	1	18
	Unspecified symptoms	0	34	1	35
Total		33	417	50	500

Most of the respondents were middle class residents.

<p>Table #149 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event? Crosstabulation</p>					
Count					
		1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event?			
		a. I forget many times	b. Sometimes I forget	c. I remember to carry everything required	Tot
Have you	Healthy	21	136	93	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

<p>been sufferin g from any of the followin g sympto ms</p>	<p>Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness , helplessness, worthlessnes s)</p>	24	15	1	40
	<p>Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)</p>	7	15	9	31
	<p>Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophren ia, delusions, hallucination s)</p>	8	6	1	15

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	4	5	5	14
Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	18	35	33	86
Epilepsy	1	6	1	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	8	10	0	18
Unspecified symptoms	6	28	1	35
Total	98	258	144	500

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Out of 500 participants 98 reported I forget many times 258 reported sometimes I forget and 144 reported I remember to carry everything required.

Table #150 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 2. How often do you engage in activities other than your academic or professional interests?

Crosstabulation

Count

		2. How often do you engage in activities other than your academic or professional interests?				Total
		a. Very Rarely, Unless forced	b.Sometimes when I find them interesting	c. I like to try out new things		
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	23	139	88	250	
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	26	11	3	40	
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	8	16	7	31	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	8	0	7	15
Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	5	9	0	14
Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	0	2	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	58	20	8	86
Epilepsy	6	2	0	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	6	9	3	18
Unspecified symptoms	13	19	3	35
Total	153	228	119	500

Out of 500 participants 153 reported very rarely unless forced, 228 reported sometimes, 119 reported I like to try out new things.

Table number 151 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 3. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?

Crosstabulation

Count

		3. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task?			
		a. I usually struggle to keep up my interest	b. I can't sustain my interest with efforts	c. I can't easily maintain my interest	Total
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	42	114	94	250
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	23	16	1	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	16	9	6	31

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	11	0	4	15
Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	4	8	2	14
Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	12	43	31	86
Epilepsy	0	7	1	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	6	8	4	18
Unspecified symptoms	12	20	3	35
Total	128	226	146	500

Out of 500 participants 128 reported I usually struggle to keep up my interest, 226 reported I can sustain interest with effort and 146 reported I can easily maintain my interest.

Table #152 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 4. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks) Crosstabulation

Count

		4. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task? (For eg: rewards, appreciation, encouraging talks)				Total
		a. I need encouraging words from time to time	b. I may sometimes need	c. I can stay motivated without much help		
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	32	117	101	250	
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	17	18	5	40	
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	18	8	5	31	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	6	0	15
Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	8	4	2	14
Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	2	0	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	38	20	28	86
Epilepsy	0	7	1	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	6	8	4	18
Unspecified symptoms	16	5	14	35
Total	147	193	160	500

Out of 500 participants 147 reported I need encouraging words from time to time 193 reported I may sometimes need and 160 reported I can stay motivated without much help.

Table #153 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 5. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse? Crosstabulation

Count		5. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse?			Total
		a. I rarely express gratitude	b. I sometimes	c. I regularly thank my family for their contributions	
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	27	105	118	250
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	2	18	20	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	9	10	12	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	6	4	5	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	3	3	8	14

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2
	Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	20	37	29	86
	Epilepsy	0	6	2	8
	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	1	12	5	18
	Unspecified symptoms	17	16	2	35
Total		86	213	201	500

Out of 500 participants 86 reported I rarely express gratitude 213 reported yes sometimes and 201 reported I regularly thank my family for their contributions.

Table #154 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 6. How often do you find yourself distracted/ confused in your daily life? Crosstabulation

Count					
		6. How often do you find yourself distracted/ confused in your daily life?			
		a.	b.	c.	
		Most	Sometime	Nev	
		of the time	s	er	Total
Have you been	Healthy	48	154	48	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	12	27	1	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	12	19	0	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	6	0	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	8	4	2	14
	Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	2	0	0	2
	Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	20	50	16	86
	Epilepsy	0	6	2	8
	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	6	10	2	18

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Unspecified symptoms	1	21	13	35
Total		119	297	84	500

Out of 500 participants 119 reported most of the time 297 reported sometimes and 84 reported never.

Table #155 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 7. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work? Crosstabulation

Count		7. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?			Total
		a. Most of the times	b. Sometimes	c. Never	
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	22	115	113	250
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	11	23	6	40

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	9	10	12	31
Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	6	0	15
Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	5	5	4	14
Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	2	0	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	14	41	31	86
Epilepsy	0	6	2	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	6	5	7	18

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Unspecified symptoms	17	18	0	35
Total		95	230	175	500

Out of 500 participants 95 reported most of their times 230 reported sometimes and 175 reported never.

Table #156 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 8. Have you anytime faced problems because of your absent-minded/ negligent behavior?

Crosstabulation

Count

		8. Have you anytime faced problems because of your absent-minded/ negligent behavior?			Total
		a. Yes, many times,	b. Yes, sometimes	c. I am careful	
Have you been	Healthy	26	146	78	250
suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	13	20	7	40

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	13	13	5	31
Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	2	4	15
Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	5	7	2	14
Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	2	0	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	16	39	31	86
Epilepsy	0	7	1	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	2	10	6	18

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Unspecified symptoms	17	3	15	35
Total		103	248	149	500

Out of 500 participants 103 reported yes many times 2 hundred and forty eight reported yes sometimes and 149 reported I am careful.

Table #157 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 9. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life? Crosstabulation

Count						
		9. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?				Total
		a. Multitasking is very difficult for me and I make mistakes	b. I sometimes make mistakes	c. Usually, I can manage multitasking		
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	28	136	86	250	
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	18	11	11	40	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	12	15	4	31
Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	14	1	0	15
Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	7	7	0	14
Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	0	1	1	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	47	27	12	86
Epilepsy	2	5	1	8

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	13	4	1	18
	Unspecified symptoms	3	30	2	35
Total		144	238	118	500

Out of 500 participants 144 reported multitasking is difficult 238 reported I sometimes make mistakes and 118 reported usually I can manage multitasking.

Table #158 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 9. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life? Crosstabulation

Count					
		9. How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?			
		a.	b.	c.	
		Multitasking is very difficult for me and I make mistakes	I sometimes make mistakes	Usually, I can manage multitasking	Total
Have you been	Healthy	28	136	86	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	18	11	11	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	12	15	4	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	14	1	0	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	7	7	0	14
	Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	0	1	1	2
	Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	47	27	12	86
	Epilepsy	2	5	1	8
	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	13	4	1	18
	Unspecified symptoms	3	30	2	35
Total		144	238	118	500

Out of 500 participants 144 reported Very likely 238 reported sometimes and 118 reported unlikely.

Table number 159 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 11.					
Can you skip daily routines like, washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?					
Crosstabulation					
Count					
		11. Can you skip daily routines like, washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?			
		a.	b.	c.	
		Mos	Sometim	No, I	
		t of the time	es	can't	Total
Have you been	Healthy	10	65	175	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	12	12	16	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	4	4	23	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	3	10	2	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	1	3	10	14
	Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	33	33	20	86
	Epilepsy	0	7	1	8
	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	4	5	9	18
	Unspecified symptoms	30	1	4	35
Total		99	141	260	500

Out of 500 participants 99 reported most of the times and 260 reported never.

Table number 160 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 12.

On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?

Crosstabulation

Count

		12. On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?			
		a. It is difficult to change my habits most of the times.	b. Sometim es, maybe	c. I am flexible to modifications.	Total
Have you been	Healthy	34	111	105	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	14	21	5	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	5	17	9	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	10	5	0	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	7	7	0	14
	Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	26	28	32	86
Epilepsy	2	4	2	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	5	9	4	18
Unspecified symptoms	31	2	2	35
Total	136	205	159	500

Out of 500 participants 136 reported it is difficult to change my habits twenty five reported sometimes and 159 reported I am flexible.

Table number 161 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 13.				
Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?				
Crosstabulation				
Count				
	13. Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?			
	a. My habits are hard to change	b. Sometimes, maybe	c. I can modify it accordingly	Total

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	17	117	116	250
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	18	15	7	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	11	9	11	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	2	4	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	9	0	5	14
	Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	27	30	29	86
Epilepsy	2	5	1	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	6	9	3	18
Unspecified symptoms	29	2	4	35
Total	129	191	180	500

Out of 500 participants 129 reported my habits are hard to change 191 reported sometimes and 180 reported I can modify.

Table number 162 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 14.					
How often have you cried, shouted, or taken your anger out of place? Crosstabulation					
Count					
	14. How often have you cried, shouted, or taken your anger out of place?				
	a. I usually can't control my feelings	b. Sometimes I can control my feelings	c. I can identify my feelings and control them	Total	
Have you been	Healthy	32	125	93	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	20	8	12	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	15	12	4	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	1	5	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	6	8	0	14
	Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	2	0	0	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	38	36	12	86
Epilepsy	4	1	3	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	4	9	5	18
Unspecified symptoms	19	1	15	35
Total	149	202	149	500

Out of 500 participants 149 reported I usually can't control my feelings 202 Sometimes and 149 reported I can identify my feelings.

Table number 163 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 15.				
Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family? Crosstabulation				
Count				
	15. Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family?			Total
	a. I often express my feelings too much/too little		c. I am aware of how much to express	
	es	Sometim	how much	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	43	113	94	250
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	26	11	3	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	10	17	4	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	10	5	0	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	5	7	2	14
	Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	2	0	0	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	37	22	27	86
Epilepsy	0	5	3	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	9	7	2	18
Unspecified symptoms	19	2	14	35
Total	162	189	149	500

Out of 500 parties weapons 162 reported I often express my feelings too much or too little, 189 reported sometimes and 149 reported I am aware of how much to express.

Table number 164 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 16.				
Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?				
Crosstabulation				
Count				
		16. Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?		
		a. My enthusiasm reduces very fast	b. Sometimes, Maybe	c. I maintain the same energy till the completion. Total
Have you been	Healthy	34	139	77
				250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	23	15	2	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	9	19	3	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	11	4	0	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	4	8	2	14
	Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	16	29	41	86
	Epilepsy	0	7	1	8
	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	6	6	6	18
	Unspecified symptoms	15	19	1	35
Total		120	247	133	500

Out 500 participants 120 reported My enthusiasm reduces fast, 247 reported sometimes, Add 133 reported I maintain the same energy.

Table number 165 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 17.

Do you find your enthusiasm reduces as the day progresses? Crosstabulation

Count					
		17. Do you find your enthusiasm reduces as the day progresses?			Total
		a. Mos t of the times	b. Sometim es	c. Nev er	
Have you been	Healthy	42	138	70	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	23	16	1	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	11	17	3	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	14	1	0	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	5	7	2	14
	Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	29	27	30	86
	Epilepsy	0	7	1	8
	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	6	10	2	18
	Unspecified symptoms	20	0	15	35
Total		151	225	124	500

Out of 500 participants 151 reported most of the times 225 reported sometimes and 124 reported never.

Table number 166-How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm? * 18.	
How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?	
Crosstabulation	
Count	
	18. How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?
	Total

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

		a. I frequently need them; it helps me keep going.	b. Sometimes, even if I don't receive it, I can manage.	c. Rewards do not affect my energy to do work.	
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	27	147	76	250
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	17	18	5	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	15	12	4	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	10	5	0	15

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	9	3	2	14
Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	0	1	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	42	26	18	86
Epilepsy	4	3	1	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	4	12	2	18
Unspecified symptoms	3	31	1	35
Total	133	257	110	500

Out of 500 participants 133 reported I frequently need them, 257 reported sometimes and 110 reported rewards do not affect my energy.

Table number 167 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 19.
How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully? Crosstabulation
Count

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

		19. How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?				Total
		a. No, I avoid myself from difficult situations	b. I take help in difficult situations	c. I can handle tough situations on my own		
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	19	128	103	250	
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	12	16	12	40	
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	8	19	4	31	
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	10	1	4	15	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	5	7	2	14
Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	8	62	16	86
Epilepsy	0	7	1	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	2	9	7	18
Unspecified symptoms	15	18	2	35
Total	81	268	151	500

Out of 500 participants 81 reported no I avoid difficult situations 268 reported I take help in difficult situations and 151 reported I can handle on my own.

Table number 168 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 20. Do you think your educational qualification/ development of skills has added to your work efficiency? Crosstabulation
Count

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

		20. Do you think your educational qualification/ development of skills has added to your work efficiency?			Total
		a. No, I do not think so	b. Sometimes, Maybe	c. Yes, it has	
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	22	74	154	250
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	20	12	8	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	3	11	17	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	12	1	2	15

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	8	4	2	14
Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	0	1	1	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	29	43	14	86
Epilepsy	1	5	2	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	2	9	7	18
Unspecified symptoms	15	17	3	35
Total	112	178	210	500

Out of 500 participants 112 reported no I do not think so 178 reporter sometimes and 210 reporter yes it has.

Table number 169 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 21.		
Do you bounce back after a failure? Crosstabulation		
Count		
	21. Do you bounce back after a failure?	Total

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

		a. Maybe, with support from family	b. Yes, with support from family	c. Yes, I can bounce back	
Have you been	Healthy	15	112	123	250
suffering from any of	Symptoms of				
the following	Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	16	14	10	40
symptoms	Symptoms of				
	Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	4	11	16	31
	Symptoms of				
	Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	2	4	15

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	6	4	4	14
Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	0	2	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	7	58	21	86
Epilepsy	0	6	2	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	2	16	0	18
Unspecified symptoms	17	16	2	35
Total	77	241	182	500

Out of 500 participants 77 reported maybe with support from family 241 reported yes with the support of family and 182 reported yes I can bounce back.

Table number 170 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 22.		
Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success? Crosstabulation		
Count		
	22. Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success?	Total

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

		a. I avoid the barriers	b. I try to cross them with support	c. I face them confidently	
Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	26	113	111	250
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	6	29	5	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	8	17	6	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	7	8	0	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	6	4	4	14

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	8	50	28	86
Epilepsy	5	0	3	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	2	13	3	18
Unspecified symptoms	30	2	3	35
Total	100	237	163	500

Out of 500 participants hundred reported I avoid the barriers 237 reported I tried to cross them with support and 163 reported I face them confidently.

Table number 171- Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 22.

Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success? Crosstabulation

Count				
	22. Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success?			Total
	a. I avoid the barriers	b. I try to cross them with support	c. I face them confidently	
Have you been Healthy	26	113	111	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	6	29	5	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	8	17	6	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	7	8	0	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	6	4	4	14
	Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	8	50	28	86
Epilepsy	5	0	3	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	2	13	3	18
Unspecified symptoms	30	2	3	35
Total	100	237	163	500

Out of 500 participants hundred reported very likely 237 reported rarely and 163 reported unlikely.

Table number 172 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 24.

Do you consider yourself an emotionally sensitive person in tough situations?

Crosstabulation

Count					
		24. Do you consider yourself an emotionally sensitive person in tough situations?			Total
		a. Mos t of the times	b. Sometim es, maybe	c. No, I am strong emotionally	
Have you been	Healthy	69	132	49	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	22	15	3	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	17	11	3	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	1	5	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	5	9	0	14
	Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	2	0	0	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	23	41	22	86
Epilepsy	0	4	4	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	4	7	7	18
Unspecified symptoms	19	15	1	35
Total	171	235	94	500

Out of 500 participants 171 reported most of the Times 235 reported sometimes and 94 reported I am strong emotionally.

Table number 174 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 25.				
Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence? Crosstabulation				
Count				
		25. Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?		
		a.	b.	c.
		Mos	Sometim	Nev
		t of the time	es	er
				Total
Have you been	Healthy	20	119	111
				250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	13	23	4	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	10	18	3	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	5	1	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	3	9	2	14
	Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	33	34	19	86
Epilepsy	0	6	2	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	1	11	6	18
Unspecified symptoms	33	1	1	35
Total	123	228	149	500

Out of 500 participants 123 reported most of the times 228 reported sometimes and 149 reported never.

Table number 175 -Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 26.

Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results? Crosstabulation

Count		26. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?			Total
		a. Most ly it does not yield the best results	b. Sometimes	c. Maximu m occasions yield the best results	
		Have you been	Healthy	21	112

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	15	13	12	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	12	14	5	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	2	4	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	3	6	5	14
	Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2
	Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	14	34	38	86
	Epilepsy	0	5	3	8
	Symptoms of Sleep disorders	2	10	6	18
	Unspecified symptoms	1	32	2	35
Total		79	229	192	500

Out of 500 participants 79 reported mostly it does not yield the best results to 229 reported sometimes and 192 reported maximum occasion yields best results.

Table #176 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 27. Do you procrastinate on your work? Crosstabulation

Count					
		27. Do you procrastinate on your work?			Total
		a.	b.	c.	
		Ma	Sometim		
		ny times,	es	I do not	
Have you been	Healthy	17	124	102	250

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

suffering from any of the following symptoms	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	20	18	2	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	16	12	3	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	1	5	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	7	3	4	14

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Personality Disorders	1	0	0	1
ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2
Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	21	41	24	86
Epilepsy	0	3	5	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	4	14	0	18
Unspecified symptoms	17	16	2	35
Total	113	233	147	500

Out of 500 participants 113 reported many times 233 reported sometimes and 147 reported never.

Table #177 - Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms * 28. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace? Crosstabulation				
Count				
	28. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?			Total
	a.	b.	c.	
	Mos t of the time	Sometim es	Nev er	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Have you been suffering from any of the following symptoms	Healthy	36	99	115	250
	Symptoms of Depression (sadness, crying episodes, hopelessness, helplessness, worthlessness)	20	12	8	40
	Symptoms of Anxiety (stress, fear, irritability, tension, palpitation, sweating, tremors)	8	13	10	31
	Symptoms of Psychosis (schizophrenia, delusions, hallucinations)	9	6	0	15
	Symptoms of OCD (recurrent intrusive thoughts, obsession for cleanliness, repeatative behavior)	9	3	2	14
	Personality Disorders	0	1	0	1
	ADHD, Autism spectrum disorders	1	1	0	2

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Substance use (Nicotene, Alcohol, Opium etc)	12	39	35	86
Epilepsy	0	5	3	8
Symptoms of Sleep disorders	4	11	3	18
Unspecified symptoms	30	1	4	35
Total	129	191	180	500

Out of 500 participants 129 reported most of the Times 191 reported sometimes and 180 reported never.

Table no 178- Distribution based on Cut off scores

	Frequency	Percentage
Pravara Sattva	3	0.6
Madhyama Sattva	221	44.2
Avara Sattva	276	55.2
Total	500	100%

Analysis of Standardisation on 500 respondents showed 276 respondents belonged to Avara sattva, 221 to Madhyama and 3 possessed Pravara Sattva.

DISCUSSION

DISCUSSION

DISCUSSION ON TOPIC OF STUDY

Sattvabala is a multifaceted construct that encompasses, memory, interest, gratitude, consciousness, cleanliness, bravery, smartness, organized behavior, all of which enables the ability to cope with adversity. It is an underrated and poorly evaluated variable despite its importance in clinical practice. It is understood as the strength of the individual to withstand difficulties with best possible outcomes to himself and to his immediate environment. Ayurveda regards Sattvabala as important as shareera bala. Numerous outcome measures in the form of diagnostic and rating scales are available today for the assessment of shareerabala/physical health. Yet, minimal assessment tools are tried on assessment of sattvabala. A poor sattva results in poor clinical outcome and is indicative of poor prognosis in healthcare. Literature survey on the present scenario revealed a dearth on assessment tool to assess sattvabala, as there were no scales available presently for the same. On literature review the description of the term 'Sattva', as 'Sattvabala' was mostly available in Charaka Samhitha Vimanasthana Rogabhishakjiteeya adhyaya, and hence the was considered for the development of the tool.

Sattvabala

This study focuses on identifying the components that necessarily contribute to the formation of Sattva and also the elements that are relevant in the assessment of Sattvabala. There is currently no assessment tool that is particular to the Ayurvedic perspective of Sattvabala. The existence of such a tool will help to provide a clear path in the diagnosis and treatment aspect.

DISCUSSION ON DOMAIN SELECTION AND ITEM GENERATION

A domain or construct refers to the concept, attribute, or unobserved behavior that is the target of the study. The first step is to define the domain(s) which is to be evaluated. A well-defined domain will provide a basic understanding of the phenomenon under study, clarify the domain boundaries, and make item development and content validation an easier process.

The domains were created based on Sattvasara laxana depicted in Charaka Samhitha Vimana Sthana Chapter 8 Rogabhishakjitiya adhyaya.

Defining the domains:

Based on the Cha. Vi.8/110- the laxana were defined. Each laxana was interpreted Based on the comprehensive search for the term from textbooks like Amara Kosha, Ashtanga Hrudaya, Ashtanga Sangraha, Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Lakshana Kosha, Hetu Kosha, Shabda Kalpadruma, Monier Williams Dictionary and Vachaspatyam.

Table no 178- Sattvasara laxana with assumed meanings for the questionnaire

Sr.No	Ayurveda Traits	Modern Traits
1	<i>Smritimanto = स्मृतिः अनुभूतार्थस्मरणं</i>	Good Memory
2	<i>Bhaktimantah = भक्तिः इच्छेत्यर्थः</i>	Interest

DISCUSSION

3	<i>Kritajna =krutam upakrutam jaanati sweekaroti yah</i>	Gratefulness
4	<i>Prajna = प्रज्ञा कालत्रयात्मिका बुद्धिः</i>	Mindfulness
5	<i>Shuchi = शुचिर्मनोवाक्कायैः शुद्धः।</i>	Purity/Cleanliness
6	<i>Mahotsaha= ऊर्जा उत्साहः, प्रयत्नः-उत्साहः, उत्साहः कार्योत्थानशक्तिः</i>	Energy, efforts, initiation
7	<i>Daksha = कर्मणि चतुरः</i>	Skillful
8	<i>Dheera = धैर्यं धीरत्वं</i>	Courage
9	<i>Smara vikarantah yodhi = समरे विक्रम्य युध्यन्तीति समरविक्रान्तयोधिनः</i>	Valour in fighting
10	<i>Tyaktavishada =given up /away despair,dejection. Exhaustion/ Balanced</i>	Absence of sorrow
11	<i>Suavyavasthitagatti = Systematic move</i>	Systematic move
12	<i>Gambhirdudhhi = Systematic planning</i>	Systematic planning
13	<i>Chesta & action</i>	Systematic action
14	<i>Kalayanaabhinivesha = कल्याणाभिनिवेशेनेति श्रेयस्करमार्गानुष्ठानेन; एतद्धि अचिरभाविश्रेयसामेव भवति</i>	Virtuous acts

DISCUSSION ON QUESTIONNAIRE DEVELOPMENT

By analysing all the data regarding domains and subdomains questions were developed. Initially a total of 44 questions were developed by literature review and direct observations. On domain wise 44 questions were on. Later through a focus group discussion it was finalised to 45 questions. Expert evaluation was done.

- Questions prepared on each domain was send for expert opinion for 22 members from different fields of Ayurveda like Manasa Roga, Clinical Psychology, English language, and those who have worked upon such studies.
- Briefed about the work, prepared a table for grading each questionnaire as essential, useful but not essential and not essential and also added a separate table for suggestions.
- Among the 22 experts, 16 of them responded back and gave suggestions regarding the work.
 - 1 Question was reframed (grammatical correction).
- In domain shuchi
 - 4 questions were retained
 - The term, ‘ Clipping the nails’ was removed from q. no. 18
 - Q. no. 23 was reframed as per expert (grammatical error)
- In domain Mahotsaha
 - 2 questions were retained
 - Q. no 25&26 question was reframed (grammatical correction)
- In Daksha domain all questions were retained

- In domain Dheera and Samaravikrantayodhina –
 - 3 questions were retained
 - Q. no. 34 was changed from “Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success” to “What do you do when you observe barriers that block the way to your success?”
- In domain suvyavysthithagatigambheerabuddhicheshta all questions were retained
- In domain Kalyanabhinivesha 2 questions were retained and 1 question was added as per the expert “ How many days a month you dedicate towards welfare of the society like cleaning neighbourhood?”
- Finally 45 items were taken for further process.

Table no.179: Domain with number of questions

Domain	Subdomain	Questions
Smriti		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How often do you forget to carry the necessary tools when attending an event? 2. How often do you recheck to ensure the work is done? 3. How often do you need help remembering important dates, events, and names of people? 4. How often do you need tricks and techniques for memory? For eg: mnemonics, sing it out, etc.
Bhakti		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How often do you engage in activities other than your academic or professional interests? 2. Do you find it difficult to sustain interest until the completion of a given task? 3. Is it common for you to only be interested in things you are familiar with? For eg: doctors who are willing to write movie reviews but unwilling to learn computer coding 4. How many times do you need someone to help you stay motivated until you finish a task?
Krutajna		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do you forget to express gratitude to your parents/spouse? 2. Do you feel that it is the parents/spouse's responsibility to take care of the family?

DISCUSSION

		3.Does your family ever remind you to say thanks for the favors received?
Prajna		<p>1. How often do you find yourself distracted/ confused in your daily life?</p> <p>2. Are you blamed for daydreaming and leaving things unattended at home/work?</p> <p>3.Have you anytime faced problems because of your absent-minded/ negligent behavior?</p> <p>4.How often do you make mistakes when multitasking in your daily life?</p> <p>5How likely do you get confused about what exactly you want to buy after coming to a shop?, confused about whether to turn right or left on the road?</p>
Shuchi	Kayashuchi	<p>1.Can you wear the same clothes for two straight days?</p> <p>2.Can you skip daily routines like washing hands, floss teeth regularly in case of urgency?</p> <p>3.On observance, and advice from others, how often do you modify personal habits?</p>
	Vakshuchi	<p>1.2Have you been blamed for talking rudely by your family?</p> <p>2.Do you find it difficult to modify your communication habits according to the situation?</p>

	Manashuchi	<p>1.How often have you cried, shouted, or taken your anger out of place?</p> <p>2.Are you blamed for not being expressive or overtly expressing your feelings by your family?</p>
Mahotsaha		<p>1.Do you find it difficult to sustain the same enthusiasm with which the task was started?</p> <p>2.Did you ever change courses/jobs because it got boring?</p> <p>3.Do you find your enthusiasm reduces as the day progresses?</p> <p>4.How often do you expect rewards or cheers from others to keep up your enthusiasm?</p>
Daksha		<p>1.How often do you manage to handle complicated situations successfully?</p> <p>2.Do you think your educational qualification/ development of skills has added to your work efficiency?</p> <p>3.Have you not received appreciation/awards/rewards for your skills in managing your duties?</p>
Dheera and Samaravikrantayodhina		<p>1.Do you believe in living a peaceful life without taking risks?</p> <p>2.Do you invest your hard-earned money and time in a new venture?</p> <p>3. Do you bounce back after a failure?</p> <p>4.Do you observe barriers can block the way to your success?</p>

Tyaktavishada		<p>1.How likely are you to lose hope when the situation does not work your way?</p> <p>2.Do you consider yourself an emotionally sensitive person in tough situations?</p> <p>3.Do you find it easy to recover emotionally after a crisis?</p>
Suvyavasthithagambhira buddhi and cheshta		<p>1.Do you consider the future consequences when you are doing work?</p> <p>2.Are you criticized by your family for carelessness and negligence?</p> <p>1. Do the efforts put in by you yield the best results?</p> <p>2. Do you procrastinate on your work?</p> <p>3. Do you often struggle to organize your home and workspace?</p>
Kalyanabhinivesha		<p>1.What is the likelihood of you considering your parents'/spouse's/children's decisions over your own?</p> <p>2.Regardless of who is at fault, do you apologize to your parents/spouse/children?</p> <p>3. How many days a month you dedicate towards welfare of the society like cleaning neighbourhood</p>

DISCUSSION

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Discussion on Likert scale

Likert response scales are widely used in survey research to measure attitudes, opinions, perceptions, and behaviors. A Likert scale typically includes a series of statements for which respondents indicate their level of agreement, often using a range from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" to responses based on "individual constructs best suited to describe the construct" as used in the current study. Here's a detailed discussion on the use of Likert responses in scale validation, touching on aspects such as design, reliability, validity, analysis, and practical considerations.

- The typical Likert scale is a 3, 4, 5- or 7-point ordinal scale used by respondents to rate the degree to which they agree or disagree with a statement. In an ordinal scale, responses can be rated or ranked, but the distance between responses is not measurable. Here a 3-point Likert scale is used. The reasons for choosing a 3-point Likert scale are:
- The 3-point Likert scale is easy to understand and apply for both survey administrators and respondents.
- It takes less time and effort to complete than higher-point scale.
- It provides respondents an option to be neutral (rather than having to choose an alternative that doesn't reflect their thinking).
- Allows for a lower margin of error; any scale without a neutral option can distort results and bring the validity of survey results into question.
- Generates reliable quantitative data that can be analysed with relative ease.

The current study was adopted with 3 point likert -(A) indicative of avara sattva, (b) indicative of Madhyama sattva and (c) indicative of pravara sattva likert response based on each question was designed.

Discussion on Statistical tests

The study was conducted in 2 phases i.e, 1) Validation and 2) Standardization phase.

Steps towards validation begins with Pilot testing of framed questionnaire, followed by Validation and Standardization. The Scale goes through several statistical tests such as

- Validity Tests
- Reliability tests
- Normality Tests
- Descriptive Statistics

Tests of Validity

Types of Validity in Scale Validation

a. Content Validity(14)

- Definition: This type of validity assesses whether the items on a scale adequately cover the construct being measured. It is not a statistical method but rather an evaluation of whether the content of the scale is representative of the domain.
- Assessment Method:
 - Expert Review: Researchers can seek opinions from subject matter experts to review items and determine whether they are relevant and comprehensive.

- High content validity is critical especially for newly developed scales. It ensures that the scale reflects the dimensions of the construct and is not biased by irrelevant items.

b. Construct Validity(2,15)

- Definition: Construct validity determines whether a scale accurately measures the theoretical construct it is intended to measure. It is often assessed through two components: convergent validity and discriminant validity.
- Statistical Techniques: Factor analysis (both exploratory and confirmatory) is a common approach to evaluate construct validity. EFA helps identify the underlying structure of the items, while CFA tests whether the data fits a proposed factor structure.
- The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test and Bartlett's test of sphericity are two statistical tests commonly used in the field of statistics, particularly in factor analysis. They help evaluate the appropriateness of data for factor analysis and assess whether relationships among the variables are sufficiently strong to justify the analysis.
- **1. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Test**
 - **a. Purpose**
 - The KMO test assesses the adequacy of sample data for factor analysis. It measures the proportion of variance among variables that might be common variance. It is an indicator of whether the data is suitable for factor analysis.
 - **b. Interpretation**
 - KMO values range from 0 to 1.

- Generally accepted thresholds for interpreting KMO values are as follows:
- **KMO < 0.50**: Poor – Sampling is not adequate.
- **0.50 < KMO < 0.60**: Mediocre – Sampling may be adequate for factor analysis, but caution is warranted.
- **0.60 < KMO < 0.70**: Acceptable – Sampling is adequate for factoring.
- **0.70 < KMO < 0.80**: Good – Sampling is likely quite adequate.
- **0.80 < KMO < 0.90**: Very Good – Sampling is strong and adequate.
- **KMO > 0.90**: Excellent – Sampling is nearly perfect.
- A higher KMO value indicates that the partial correlations between variables are relatively small, suggesting that factor analysis may be appropriate.

2) Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

- a. Purpose
- Bartlett's test assesses whether the correlation matrix of the data significantly differs from an identity matrix. It tests the null hypothesis that the variables are unrelated, meaning that factor analysis may not be appropriate.
- b. Interpretation
- If the p-value from Bartlett's test is less than a significance level (commonly set at 0.05), the null hypothesis of sphericity is rejected. This indicates that there are significant correlations among the variables, justifying the use of factor analysis.

Discussion on Factor Analysis

Principle component analysis is the Factor analysis method used in this study. PCA is used to simplify complex data by identifying a small number of principal components which capture the maximum variance. PCA achieve data simplification by identifying the number of components which explain the set of observed variables (Component

retention). The relationship between an observed variable and a component is expressed by a factor loading (ranging from 0 to 1), which measures the amount of the variance in the variable explained by the component. A factor loading of >0.4 generally indicates that the variable can be attributed to the factor. A factor loading matrix shows the relationship between the factors and the original variables, with components typically named by the common attributes of the set of variables with which they are most correlated. A factor rotation allows for an infinite number of possible representations. In this study Varimax rotation is used to maximize simplicity and interpretation.

Reasons why Principal Component Analysis was used:

- PCA aims to explain the maximum amount of the total variance in the variables by analyzing all of the observed variance.
- PCA is undertaken when there is sufficient correlation among the original variables.
- PCA reduces the number of variables extracting the essence of the dataset by creating principal components.

The Principal Component Analysis and varimax rotation was run for the 45 items with 300 samples. The distribution broke into 28 components, out of which 10 components had eigenvalue more than 1. So, 10 principal components were extracted. The 10 factors loaded between 0.535 to 0.8 showing a simpler structure and better inter variable associations.

Limitations of Validity Tests(2)

- Construct Overlap: Constructs can be complex and overlapping, which can confound the results. For example, traits like anxiety and depression may correlate, making it difficult to establish distinct validity for each.
- Cultural Differences: Validity assessments may need to account for cultural

differences in how items are interpreted or respond to scale options. Constructs may manifest differently across populations, affecting validity.

- Criterion and predictive validity tests were not taken up due to inavailability of scales measuring similar constructs.

Tests of Reliability(2,16)

Reliability is a key aspect of scale validation, as it refers to the consistency and stability of a measure. A reliable scale produces consistent results across different instances of measurement. Establishing the reliability of a scale is essential because even if a scale is valid (measuring what it is intended to measure), it must also yield results that are stable and replicable. There are several methods to assess the reliability of scales, often depending on the type of data and the specific context of the research.

1. Types of Reliability Tests

- a. **Internal Consistency** Internal consistency assesses whether items on the scale are measuring the same underlying construct. A common measure of internal consistency is Cronbach's alpha.
- **Assessment Method:**
 - **Cronbach's Alpha:** This statistic ranges from 0 to 1, where values above 0.70 are generally considered acceptable, and values above 0.90 may indicate excessive redundancy (i.e., items are too similar).
 - **Split-Half Reliability:** This involves dividing the scale into two halves (e.g., odd versus even items) and correlating the scores from both halves. A high correlation indicates good reliability.
 - **b. Test-Retest Reliability**
 - **Definition:** Test-retest reliability measures the stability of a scale over time. It assesses whether individuals respond similarly when the same scale is administered at two different points in time.
 - A high correlation coefficient (typically above 0.80) indicates strong test-retest reliability.
 - **Homogeneity of the Sample:** The variability within a sample can affect reliability statistics. A more homogeneous sample might yield higher reliability estimates than a diverse sample.

Limitations of Reliability Tests(17)

Contextual Dependence: Reliability is not absolute; a scale may be reliable in one context but not in another. Therefore, reliability should be established for each specific population and setting.

Situational or Temporal Variability: Factors such as changes in respondents' moods, environments, or circumstances can affect responses, thus impacting reliability.

Tests of Normality(2,18)

Norm development is an essential process in psychometrics, focusing on establishing standards or benchmarks for interpreting scores on a particular measure. Norms provide context for individual scores, allowing researchers and practitioners to compare their results against a representative sample or population. This comparison can help determine an individual's position relative to others using the same scale, and thus enhance the interpretability of the data.

When developing norms, certain statistical tests and methodologies are utilized to ensure that the resulting norms are valid, reliable, and applicable to the intended population.

Statistical Tests for Norm Development

a. Descriptive Statistics

- **Mean and Standard Deviation:** The mean (average score) and standard deviation (variability of scores around the mean) are fundamental statistics used to describe the normative sample. These figures allow clinicians and researchers to understand the central tendency and dispersion of scores.
- **Percentiles and Standard Scores:** Percentiles indicate the relative standing of a score in a normative distribution. For instance, if a score is at the 75th cut, it is higher than 75% of the normative sample. Standard scores (like z-scores)

translate raw scores into a common scale, allowing for comparison across different measures.

DISCUSSION ON FIRST SET OF STUDY – Pilot Study

Considering the assessment of face validity modifications to grammar, word choice, and answer options were made.

DISCUSSION ON SECOND SET OF STUDY – Validation Study

Validation was taken up on 300 healthy volunteers thus making sure of sampling adequacy. Despite lower Cronbach's alpha and KMO domain wise, whole construct involving 45 items provided adequate to good reliability and satisfactory factor analysis. Most of the respondents opted response on Madhyama sattva, thus ensuring their health status. However the questions on the domain Kalyanabhinivesha was seen to be difficult to comprehend based on poor statistical item total correlation and communality values thus making it poorly understood domain and hence was eliminated.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis was further done which resulted in elimination of 17 items thus retaining 28 items.

DISCUSSION ON THIRD SET OF STUDY – STANDARDISATION STUDY

The study conducted on 500 samples was conducted with the questionnaire refined after validation with 10 domains and 28 items. It involved healthy volunteers and patients which facilitated at screening avara sattva as the population of patients generated lower score, thus facilitating norm development and establishing the cut off scores.

The final assessment tool consisted of a total of 10 domains with 28 items.

Conclusion

Conclusion

In the process of validating and standardizing a scale for measuring Sattvabala, several key findings emerged that underline the significance and effectiveness of the instrument developed.

1. Construct Validity: Through exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses, the scale demonstrated strong construct validity. The dimensions of Sattvabala, reflecting mental strength, clarity, and resilience, were well-represented, confirming that the scale accurately measures the intended construct.

2. Reliability: The scale exhibited high internal consistency, as indicated by Cronbach's alpha coefficients exceeding the acceptable threshold. This suggests that items within the scale are measuring the same underlying concept consistently, offering confidence in the tool's reliability over repeated administrations.

3. Normative Data: Standardization efforts provided normative data, allowing for comparisons across different populations. This is essential for interpreting individual scores in context, enhancing the scale's utility in both clinical and research settings.

4. Practical Application: The standardized scale of Sattvabala can serve various applications, including clinical assessments, therapeutic interventions, and research studies focusing on psychological resilience and well-being.

5. Future Directions: Ongoing research may focus on longitudinal studies to assess the scale's sensitivity to change over time and its relevance in diverse cultural contexts. Additionally, exploring the correlations between Sattvabala and other psychological constructs could enrich our understanding of mental resilience.

In summary, the validation and standardization of the Sattvabala scale affirm its reliability and relevance as a measure of mental strength and well-being. Its implementation can provide

Conclusion

insights into individual and group psychological states, ultimately contributing to more effective interventions and strategies in mental health and personal development domains.

SUMMARY

Title: Validation and Standardisation of a tool to assess Sattvabala

Background: The concept of *Sattvabala*, rooted in Ayurveda, encompasses mental clarity, emotional stability, and overall psychological resilience to combat adversities. This study aimed to validate and standardize a tool designed to assess *Sattvabala*, thus providing a reliable measure for both clinical and research purposes. The development process included a comprehensive literature review, expert consultations, and iterative feedback to ensure the tool's relevance and comprehensiveness. A cross-sectional study was conducted involving a diverse sample of participants, including practitioners of Ayurveda and individuals seeking holistic health assessments. Factor analysis was employed to ascertain the underlying structure of the assessment tool, while reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha and test-retest methods. The results demonstrated strong psychometric properties, with the final version of the tool comprising multiple dimensions that accurately reflect the constructs of *Sattvabala*. This standardized tool not only enhances the assessment of sattva in clinical practice but also provides a foundational framework for future research exploring the interplay between psychological states and physical health. The findings underscore the importance of incorporating traditional concepts into contemporary health assessments, promoting a more holistic understanding of well-being.

Objectives: To validate and standardize an Ayurveda assessment tool for Sattvabala.

Sample Size -800

Methods:

This study outlines the methodology applied to validate and standardize a newly developed tool

SUMMARY

for assessing *Sattvabala*, a core concept in Ayurveda representing mental and emotional resilience. The research was conducted in several phases:

1. **Tool Development:** Initially, an extensive literature review was performed to define *Sattvabala* and identify relevant indicators. Expert consultations with Manasaroga practitioners, language experts and psychologists were conducted to generate a comprehensive item pool, capturing different dimensions of *Sattvabala*.
2. **Pilot Testing:** A preliminary version of the assessment tool was administered to a small group of participants (n=18) to evaluate clarity and relevance of the items. Feedback was collected to refine the tool.
3. **Main Study Design:** A cross-sectional study was conducted with a diverse sample of 300 healthy participants ranging in age, gender, and cultural background. Participants were sent across google forms.
4. **Data Collection:** The refined *Sattvabala* tool, consisting of 45 items on a 3-point Likert scale, was distributed alongside established measures of psychological resilience and well-being for comparative analysis. Demographic data were also collected.
5. **Statistical Analysis:** Factor analysis (Principal Component Analysis) was performed to determine the dimensional structure of the tool, while reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha to evaluate internal consistency. Test-retest reliability was examined with a subset of participants (n=300) within the next few weeks.
6. **Validity Assessment:** Construct validity was assessed by correlating scores from the *Sattvabala* tool with external measures of mental health and emotional well-being. Content validity was established through expert reviews and qualitative feedback.
7. **Standardisation Phase:** 28 items were retained from the 45 items scale post CFA and a 28 item questionnaire was sent across 500 participants (250 healthy and 250 patients of

SUMMARY

Common Mental Disorders) and cut off scores were finalised based on Normality tests and Z score calculation

8. **Finalization of Tool:** Findings from the analysis led to the finalization of a 28-item assessment tool, showcasing robust psychometric properties indicating high reliability and validity.

RESULTS: The observations are presented in the form of tables and graphs. The developed assessment tool displays Cronbach's alpha and KMO values that are statistically significant. As a result, the tool has been appropriately validated. Further norm development results and cut off scores are compiled in tables and the final scale is framed.

CONCLUSION: The study provides an assessment tool which is validated and standardized on Sattvabala. After the thorough research through Samhitas and other related texts, a total of 28 items were standardized post validation following the steps in tool development.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

BIBILOGRAPHY

1. Charak Samhita [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Oct 29]. Rogabhisagjitiya Vimana. Available from: https://www.carakasamhitaonline.com/mediawiki-1.32.1/index.php?title=Rogabhisagjitiya_Vimana
2. Boateng GO, Neilands TB, Frongillo EA, Melgar-Quiñonez HR, Young SL. Best Practices for Developing and Validating Scales for Health, Social, and Behavioral Research: A Primer. *Front Public Health*. 2018 Jun 11;6:149.
3. www.wisdomlib.org. Sattva, Sāttva, Shattva: 25 definitions [Internet]. 2012 [cited 2024 Oct 29]. Available from: <https://www.wisdomlib.org/definition/sattva>
4. E SAMHITHA - CHARAKA SUTRASATHANA 11/36 CHAKRAPANI COMMENTARY [Internet]. NIIMH; 204AD. Available from: <https://niimh.nic.in/ebooks/ecaraka/?mod=read&h=sattva>
5. E SUSHRUTHA SAMHITHA SUTRASTHANA 35TH CHAPTER ATUROPAKRAMANIYA ADHYAYA 38TH SHLOKA. NIIMH; 2024.
6. E ASHTANGA SANGRAHA VAGBHATA SUTRA STHANA 5TH CHAPTER/30TH VERSE [Internet]. VEDOTPATTI; Available from: <https://www.vedotpatti.in/samhita/Vag/esangraha/?mod=read&h=sattva>
7. E ASHTANGA HRIDAYA SUTRASTANA 1/29 SARVANGA SUNDARI TEEKA [Internet]. VEDOTPATTI; Available from: <https://www.vedotpatti.in/samhita/Vag/ehrudayam/?mod=read&h=sattva>

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

8. Applied Psychometrics: The Steps of Scale Development and Standardization Process [Internet]. [cited 2024 Oct 29]. Available from: <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=87941>
9. Bannigan K, Watson R. Reliability and validity in a nutshell. *J Clin Nurs*. 2009 Dec;18(23):3237–43.
10. Ahmed I, Ishtiaq S. Reliability and validity: Importance in Medical Research. *JPMA J Pak Med Assoc*. 2021 Oct;71(10):2401–6.
11. polguart. Module 2 – Qualities of a good Measuring Instrument [Internet]. polguart. 2010 [cited 2024 Oct 29]. Available from: <https://polguart.wordpress.com/2010/03/17/module-2-qualities-of-a-good-measuring-instrument/>
12. Andrade C. Z Scores, Standard Scores, and Composite Test Scores Explained. *Indian J Psychol Med*. 2021 Oct 10;43(6):555.
13. Abbasi N, Ghosh S. Construction and Standardization of Examination Anxiety Scale for Adolescent Students. *Int J Assess Tools Educ*. 2020 Dec 20;7(4):522–34.
14. Content Validity - an overview | ScienceDirect Topics [Internet]. [cited 2024 Oct 29]. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/nursing-and-health-professions/content-validity>
15. Construct Validity - an overview | ScienceDirect Topics [Internet]. [cited 2024 Oct 29]. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/social-sciences/construct-validity>
16. 4.2 Reliability and Validity of Measurement – Research Methods in Psychology

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

- [Internet]. [cited 2024 Oct 29]. Available from: <https://opentext.wsu.edu/carriecuttler/chapter/reliability-and-validity-of-measurement/>
17. Ambuehl B, Inauen J. Contextualized Measurement Scale Adaptation: A 4-Step Tutorial for Health Psychology Research. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022 Oct 6;19(19):12775.
 18. White RF, Braun JM, Kopylev L, Segal D, Sibrizzi CA, Lindahl AJ, et al. Part 1: Principles for Evaluating Psychometric Tests. In: NIEHS Report on Evaluating Features and Application of Neurodevelopmental Tests in Epidemiological Studies: NIEHS Report 01 [Internet] [Internet]. National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences; 2022 [cited 2024 Oct 29]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK581902/>

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES